

D3.5 – Report of EURAKNOS workshop 2

EURAKNOS

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

TASK 3.5

Summary

Task description:

WP 3 aims to design a High Impact Knowledge Reservoir (HIKR). More specifically WP3 will set the standards for a harmonised approach and will come up with the best design and format for a HIKR of TNs and other multi-actor projects (MAPs), based on the outcomes of the evaluation of 28 TNs carried out in WP2. While Task 3.1 focuses on best data practices and methodologies, Task 3.2 looks to the design of such a HIKR, Task 3.3 to best dissemination, communication, and exploitation strategies, and Task 3.4 to the multi-actor approach. Task 3.5 will support the aforementioned Tasks, integrate the vision paper of the Strategic Innovation Board on the Future of an EU wide common knowledge reservoir for agriculture and forestry, and develop technical Guidelines for a HIKR. These recommendations will be presented during a 2-day workshop.

This report represents the outline, methodologies, and main results of this second EURAKNOS workshop. During this workshop, the HIKR technical Guidelines, presented in the TN Explorer's Guide, were discussed, added to, and validated by KIP members, amongst which were farmers & advisors and TN coordinators, the two main end-user groups of EURAKNOS. Due to the COVID-19 situation, the originally planned workshop on 27-29 April in Tallinn, Estonia, had to be replaced by a series of webinars that took place between 11 and 20 May 2020.

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	E	Ethics	
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	CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium	

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List of abbreviations

4D4F – Data Driven Dairy Decision For Farmers
 ACTA – Association de Coordination Technique Agricole
 AKIS – Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
 AU – Aarhus University
 AUA – Agricultural University of Athens
 CAP – Common Agricultural Policy
 EC – European Commission
 EIP-AGRI – Agricultural European Innovation Partnership
 ENRD – European Network for Rural Development
 EURAKNOS – Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs: towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System
 EUREKA – European Knowledge Repository for Best Agricultural Practices
 EV ILVO – Eigen Vermogen van het Instituut voor Landbouw- en Visserijonderzoek
 e-KRP – electronic Knowledge Reservoir Platform
 GDPR – General Data Protection Regulation
 GLZ – Gruenlandzetrum Niedersachsen/Bremen EV
 HIKR – High Impact Knowledge Reservoir
 ICROFS – International Centre for Research in Organic Food Systems
 IDELE – Institut de l’Elevage
 IfA – Innovation for Agriculture
 IFOAM – International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements European Union Regional Group
 KIP – Knowledge Innovation Panel
 KR – Knowledge Reservoir
 LFG – Leap Forward Group
 MA – Multi-actor
 MAA –Multi-Actor Approach
 NAIK – Nemzeti Agrárkutató és Innovációs Központ
 NAK – Magyar Agrar-, Élel miszergazdasági Es Videkfejlesztési Kamara
 NRN – National Rural Network
 OG – Operational Group
 PA – Practical Abstract
 PLAID – Peer-to-Peer learning: accessing innovation through demonstration
 PSKW – Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt Sint-Katelijne-Waver
 RAU – Royal Agricultural University
 SKIN – Short supply chains Knowledge & Innovation Network
 SME – Small and medium-sized enterprises
 TN – Thematic Network
 UGent – Ghent University
 USC – Universidad de Santiago de Compostela
 WP – Work Package

1. Introduction

EURAKNOS has developed the Thematic Network (TN) Explorer’s Guide (D3.6) based on Thematic Networks’ best practices regarding knowledge-gathering, effective communication and dissemination strategies, and the multi-actor approach. The Guide was developed with input from the Knowledge Innovation Panel (KIP), a group of multi-actors including representatives of TNs and end-users from the agriculture and forestry sector. The concept of the Guide is to help consortia that are preparing a proposal for a TN, or that have already received funding but have not yet completed the project, to work effectively and create more impact based on the experience of previous TNs.

A series of 7 online webinars was held between 11 and 20 May to present the draft version of the TN Explorer’s Guide to the KIP and to further develop and validate its content. These online sessions successfully replaced the planned workshop in Tallinn, which could not take place due to the COVID-19 crisis. A total of 63 people participated in at least one of the webinars, where the organizers had to develop new skills such as participatory distance facilitation to implement online tools such as Zoom (for the meeting itself), Mentimeter¹ and PolleEv² (for carrying out polls), and MURAL³ (for interactive participation where everyone could place sticky notes on a board). The participants also learned about how to participate, and be active in such webinars.

Figure 1. Participants in every session

First, all participants were introduced to the TN Explorer’s Guide a week beforehand and asked to read the 33 pages as homework. The following week there was an introductory webinar followed with 6 sessions about specific aspects of a TN:

- The roles of different actors involved in TNs’ Multi Actor Approach (MAA)
- Assessing end-user needs and identifying the best way to collect and generate user-friendly knowledge.
- Designing a strategy for end-user engagement
- Improvement of the usual format for practice abstracts
- Design and strategy for a future database and how TNs can present themselves on a digital platform
- Increasing impact and sustainability

¹ <https://www.mentimeter.com/>

² <https://www.polleverywhere.com/>

³ <https://www.mural.co/>

The participants were very active and all input will be used to further improve the TN Explorer's Guide, which will be finalised during the summer and made public by the end of 2020.

Many participants found these webinars very useful and inspiring. Some even mentioned that the sessions were already being used as inspiration and as templates for online collaboration in other projects.

1.1. Context

The EURAKNOS Workshop 2 was a part of WP3, Task 3.5: Design a High Impact Knowledge Reservoir (HIKR). WP3 first built on the outcome of WP2, in which running and finalised TNs were analysed regarding types of knowledge and data formats, the knowledge reservoir, communication and dissemination strategies, and strategies for the multi-actor (MA) approach. This was presented and discussed with the knowledge innovation panel (KIP) at EURAKNOS workshop 1 in Budapest September 2019, which resulted in the 20 recommendations for TN best practices and methodologies (see D2.5 Report of EURAKNOS workshop 1 and D2.6 Summary on current practices and methodologies of TNs). Based on this knowledge, Task 3.1 dealt with best methodologies and practices to generate, select, collect and store knowledge and data as outputs of TNs (see D3.1 Report on HIKR methodologies and practices for data generation, selection, collection, and storage), Task 3.2 defined the design of a common format and tools (software, data formats) to be used for a HIKR (see D3.2 Report on HIKR Design), Task 3.3 selected the main tools to disseminate, communicate and inform end-users (see D3.3 Report on HIKR strategies to disseminate, communicate to the end-user and exploit on innovative knowledge and data), Task 3.3 also proposed a new EIP-AGRI set of common formats for practice abstracts (see D3.6 HIKR technical Guidelines) and Task 3.4 selected the main tools to involve multi-actors in TNs with focus on the end-user in the different phases of the project: conceptualisation, initiation, execution, and post-execution of the project (see D3.4 Report on the HIKR multi-actor approach).

1.2. Objectives

The overall objective of the workshop was to share, discuss, and validate EURAKNOS' best experiences identified from finalised and ongoing TNs in the form of technical Guidelines presented in the TN Explorer's Guide, on:

- data collected
- how to store data and to design a platform
- how to communicate and disseminate
- how to manage the multi-actor approach

2. Task members

Table 1. Partners involved in the different Tasks of WP3 (in bold the task leaders).

Task	Partner													EV ILVO
	ACTA	IDELE	NAK	UGent	GLZ	USC	AU	PSKW	ARC	AUA	IFA	LFG	RAU	
3.1		X	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			x	x	
3.2		X	x	x			x	x	x			x	x	
3.3	x	x	x	x	x	x		x			x	x	x	
3.4	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	
3.5	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

3. Methodology

The work performed in WP3 was primarily based on a co-design and multi-actor approach among TNs. This entailed that each task organised a working group meeting with specific actors from the knowledge innovation panel (KIP), who were actively engaged in relevant work in running or finalised TN or who were in other ways considered as relevant actors to engage in each working group. The four working groups were organised at the same time and location to facilitate exchange between the working groups, but the main part of the time work was going on in each separate group. The outcome of these working groups formed the basis of the first draft of the TN Explorer's Guide (also see D3.1, D3.2, D3.3, and D3.4).

After these working group meetings in Paris in December 2019, the task leaders of WP3 met together with the coordinator of EURAKNOS and a few other relevant participants in Brussels (and online) in February 2020. Here the plan for the 'TN Explorer's Guide' was laid out and the plan for EURAKNOS workshop 2 in Tallinn, Estonia, in April 2020 was finalised. The Knowledge Innovation Panel (KIP) (> 100 members), and 29 external participants had already signed up for it.

Due to the outbreak of COVID-19, the workshop was cancelled, and instead, the WP3 team discussed how to reach the goals with the meeting. It was decided to change one physical two-day workshop into 7 online webinars of each 1-1½ hour. The EURAKNOS workshop 2 was therefore replaced by a series of webinars on May 11, 18, 19, and 20, 2020. Participants were invited to take part in all or one or a few of the webinars depending upon their availabilities, interests, and preferences.

The KIP, including TN coordinators, and the EURAKNOS, and EUREKA⁴ consortia were invited. 70 people (including the organisers) participated in one or more of the webinars.

Taking into account the new situation that everyone had to face due to the Covid-19 outbreak, the people who took part to the workshops matched the initial expectations of participants that would have taken part to the Tallin workshop. The fact that the workshop was online and not physical, might have facilitate the participation during the webinars. A significant number of TN coordinators, researchers, advisors etc. were present, hence the knowledge and expertise of participants was represented on a higher level, matching the initial expectations. In Table 1 the background of the participants is explained when it was possible to retrieve the information.

⁴ Sisterproject from EURAKNOS, <https://www.h2020eureka.eu/>

Table 1: Description of participants per workshop

Kick-off webinar May 11th 2020: Guide to enter the onlinemeeting, prerequisite for the upcoming workshops (Total number of participants 48)	
Number of participants	Actors
21	EURAKNOS Consortium
3	Advisors
4	Consultants
3	Farmers
1	IT professional
1	Policymaker
15	Researchers
<p>Participants attended the webinar, made up of agricultural researchers, social scientists, advisors, consultants, policy makers, facilitators and coordinators of existing TNs, as follows: INCREDIBLE⁵ (n= 1), SheepNet⁶ (n=2), EUPig⁷ (n=2), SKIN⁸ (n=1), OK NET ARABLE⁹ (n=2), CERERE¹⁰ (n = 2), Agrispin¹¹ (n=2), PLAID¹² (n=1) Roadmap¹³ (n = 2), NEFERTITI¹⁴ (n=1) DESIRA¹⁵ (n=2), FERTINNOWA¹⁵ (n=1), FAIRshare¹⁶ (n=3) as well as communication and dissemination experts (n=4). A representative from the TITRIS database project (Lithuania) was present (n=1).</p>	
Session 2 – May 18 th 2020: The roles of different actors in the Multi Actor Approach in Thematic Networks (Total number of participants 39).	
Number of participants	Background
22	EURAKNOS Consortium
2	Advisors
4	Consultants
2	Policymaker
9	Researchers
<p>Participants present here had different backgrounds. Social scientists as well as agricultural engineers were present. Amongst other, links were indicated with TNs OK-Net EcoFeed¹⁷ (n=1), CERERE (n=1), EUREKA¹⁸ (n=1), FAIRshare (n=1), INCREDIBLE (n= 1), SheepNet (n=1), EUPig (n=1), SKIN (n=1), OK NET ARABLE (n=1), CERERE (n = 1), Agrispin (n=1), PLAID (n=1) Roadmap (n = 1), NEFERTITI (n=1) DESIRA (n = 1), FERTINNOWA (n=1), FAIRshare (n=1) as well as communication and dissemination experts.</p>	
Session 3 – May 18 th 2020: Assessing end-user needs and identifying the best ways to harvest and co-generate user-friendly knowledge (Total number of participants 36).	
Number of participants	Background
16	EURAKNOS Consortium
3	Advisors
2	Consultants
1	Farmers
1	IT professional

1	Policymaker
11	Researchers
1	SME
8	Not identified
<p>Participants present here had different backgrounds. Social scientists as well as agricultural engineers were present. Amongst other, links were indicated with TNs OK net Arable (n=3) & OK-Net EcoFeed (n=1), CERERE (n=1), EUREKA (n=4), FAIRshare (n=1), FERTINNOWA (n=1), Hennovation¹⁹ (n=1), Inno4Grass²⁰ (n=1), SmartProtect²¹ (n=2) , Winetwork²² (n=2), Incredible (n=1), SKIN (n=2), and I2Connect²³ (n=2) as well as with H2020 MAPS DISCONTTOOLS²⁴ (n=2), LIAISON²⁵ (n=3). Again the representative from the TITRIS²⁶ database project (Lithuania) participated (n=1).</p>	
<p>Session 4 – May 19th 2020: Designing your end-userengagement strategy (Total number of participants 35).</p>	
Number of participants	Background
17	EURAKNOS Consortium
3	Advisors
2	Consultants
2	Policymaker
11	Researchers
<p>Participants attended the webinar, made up of agricultural researchers, social scientists, advisors, consultants, policy makers, facilitators and coordinators of existing TNs, as follows: EURAKNOS (n = 17), INCREDIBLE TN (n= 2), SheepNet (n=1), EUPig (n=1), Newbie (n=2), SKIN (n=1), OK NET ARABLE (n=1), CERERE (n = 1), Organic PLUS (n=1), Agrispin (n=1), PLAID (n=1) Roadmap (n = 1), NEFERTITI (n=1) DESIRA (n = 1), FERTINNOWA (n=1), FAIRshare (n=1), and Legumes Translated²⁶ (n=1), as well as communication and dissemination experts (n = 2).</p>	
<p>Session 5 – May 19th 2020: Improving the common format of practice abstract (Total number of participants 31).</p>	
Number of participants	Background
17	EURAKNOS Consortium
2	Advisors
1	Consultants
1	Policymaker
10	Researchers
<p>Session 6 – May 20th, 2020 10:00-11:00: Design and strategy of the future database and how TNs can present themselves on the digital platform (Total number of participants 31).</p>	
Number of participants	Background
17	EURAKNOS Consortium
3	Advisors

1	Consultants
1	IT professional
2	Policymaker
6	Researchers
1	SME
<p>Participants attended the webinar, made up of agricultural researchers, social scientists, advisors, consultants, policy makers, facilitators and coordinators of existing TNs, as follows: INCREDIBLE TN (n= 1), SheepNet (n=1), EUPig (n=1), SKIN (n=1), OK NET ARABLE (n=1), CERERE (n = 1), Agrispin (n=1), PLAID (n=1) Roadmap (n = 1), NEFERTITI (n=1) DESIRA (n = 1), FERTINNOWA (n=1), FAIRshare (n=1) as well as communication and dissemination experts (n = 1). A representative from the TITRIS database project (Lithuania) was present (n=1).</p>	
<p>Session 7–May 20th,2020: Increasing impact and sustainability (Total number of participants 34).</p>	
Number of participants	Background
17	EURAKNOS Consortium
3	Advisors
4	Consultants
1	Policymaker
9	Researchers
1	SME
7	Not identified
<p>Participants attended the webinar, made up of agricultural researchers, social scientists, advisors, consultants, policy makers, facilitators and coordinators of existing TNs, as follows: INCREDIBLE (n=1) , EUREKA (n=6), EUPiG (n=2), NEWBIE (n=1), OK-Arable Net (n=1), CORE-ORGANIC (n=3), 4D4F²⁷(n=2), Organic PLUS (n=2), CERERE (n=2), DESIRA (n=2), Roadmap (n=2)and NEFERTITI (n=1).</p>	

⁵ <https://www.incredibleforest.net/>

⁶ <http://www.sheepnet.network/>

⁷ <http://www.eupig.eu/>

⁸ <http://shortfoodchain.eu/>

⁹ <http://ok-net-arable.eu/en>

¹⁰ <http://cerere2020.eu/>

¹¹ <https://agrispin.eu/>

¹² <https://plaid-h2020.eu/>

¹³ <https://www.roadmap-h2020.eu/>

¹⁴ <https://nefertiti-h2020.eu/>

¹⁵ <http://desira2020.eu/>

¹⁶ <https://www.h2020fairshare.eu/>

¹⁷ <https://ok-net-ecofeed.eu/>

¹⁸ <https://h2020eureka.eu/>

¹⁹ <http://www.hennovation.eu/>

²⁰ <https://www.inno4grass.eu/en/>

²¹ <https://www.smartprotect-h2020.eu/>

²² <http://www.winetwork.eu/>

²³ <https://i2connect-h2020.eu/>

²⁴ <https://www.discontools.eu/>

²⁵ <https://liaison2020.eu/>

²⁶ <https://www.legumestranslated.eu/>

²⁷ <https://4d4f.eu/>

The webinars were conducted using ZOOM, hosted by Aarhus University, which as a part of a European collaboration between universities has a special licence hosted in the EU so that EU GDPR rules apply. Despite this, some potential participants were not allowed by their organisations to participate using ZOOM. As a supplement to a presentation, in several of the webinars the survey systems Mentimeter or PollEverywhere were being used to ask participants questions and in this way create an interactive atmosphere. In some cases, when participating on a smart-phone, the participants could not see the screen presentation on the computer, however, if the presentation being shown was shown through Mentimeter, this had the advantage that people could see the “slides” in Mentimeter directly on their smartphone. In addition to Mentimeter, also the application MURAL was used. MURAL works much to list a post-it board/flip-over chart, where all participants online can write on post-its and put on the board. It can even stay open after the webinar has ended so that participants can keep working on it after the end of the webinar.

The first webinar on May 11th 2020 was an introduction to the workshop and webinar series as well as to the TN Explorer’s Guide draft version.

From May 11th to 18th the participants were requested to read ‘The TN Explorer’s Guide’ and to prepare their reactions to specific questions. In Annex I, you can find all the material sent to the participants after the first webinar for their preparation of the following webinars.

A note on the style of the Explorer’s Guide: mobilising thematic networks and the multi-actor approach is not a one size fits all process. Although the Guide includes tools and recommendations from EURAKNOS’ analysis and consultations, the Guide also contains a lot of questions. This is deliberately designed to engage the reader in active reflecting on the processes required to facilitate their thematic network.

The webinars were recorded and due to GDPR participation was only possible after filling in a consent form. This can also be found in Annex II.

STEP 1: Kick-off webinar

Main objective: presentation of the ‘EURAKNOS Thematic Network Explorer’s Guide’

Timetable: 11th May at 11 am CET (1 hour)

STEP 2: Individual 'homework'

Main objective: reading the ‘EURAKNOS Thematic Network Explorer’s Guide’

Timetable: during the week beginning 11th May (33 pages, 2 - 3 hours)

STEP 3: Series of participative webinars

Main objective: presentation of the ‘EURAKNOS Thematic Network Explorer’s Guide’ and discussing and getting input for the further development of the Guide.

Timetable: 18-19-20 May 2020 (1-1½ hours)

Table 2. Programme for webinars presenting and discussing EURAKNOS Explorer’s Guide

Date and time	Topic	Presenters	YOUR outcome of participating	We wish from you	Preparation
SESSION 1 11th May 11:00 – 12:00	Introduction to the “EURAKNOS Explorer’s Guide” Introduction to the methodology of the workshops. Explanation of how to choose between workshops next week.	Ilse A. Rasmussen & Maxime Marois	An overview of the Guide on how to prepare and run a Thematic Network (TN)	Being aware Being open-minded	None
Homework	May 11 th to 18 th we kindly ask you to read “The Thematic Network Explorer’s Guide” now 30 pp, sorry - and prepare answers to specific questions. May 11 th you receive both EURAKNOS “The Thematic Network Explorer’s Guide” and the questions for your homework.				
SESSION 2 18th May 10:00 – 11:00	The roles of different actors in the Multi Actor Approach in Thematic Networks	Elodie Pascal, Sylvia Burssens & Laurens Van der Cruyssen	Who, When, How different actors are valuable to a TN	Participate in the discussion	Read “The Thematic Network Explorer’s Guide” chapter 2 & 3
SESSION 3 18th May 14:00 – 15:00	Assessing end-user needs and identifying the best ways to harvest and co-generate user-friendly knowledge	Maxime Marois & Patrick Sarzeaud	Influence the EURAKNOS Explorer’s Guide regarding end-user needs	Your feedback to integrate in the Guidelines for the future TNs	Read “The Thematic Network Explorer’s Guide” chapter 4
SESSION 4 19th May 10:00 – 11:00	Designing your end-user engagement strategy	Lisa Williams van Dijk & Jessica Stokes	How to validate the dissemination and exploitation pathways	Participation in surveys during the session	Read “The Thematic Network Explorer’s Guide” Sections 2.2, 4.4 and 4.5
SESSION 5 19th May 14:00 – 15:00	Improving the common format of practice abstract	Lisa Williams van Dijk & Jessica Stokes	Insight into different ways to disseminate	Your votes for different formats	Read “The Thematic Network Explorer’s Guide” Please follow specific instructions for session 5.

SESSION 6 20th May 10:00 – 11:30	Design and strategy of the future database and how TNs can present themselves on the digital platform	Laurens Van der Cruyssen, Davino Van Hall & Hercules Panoutsopoulos	Influence the EURAKNOS Explorer's Guide regarding future database	Your input on how TNs want to present themselves on the platform.	Read "The Thematic Network Explorer's Guide" chapter 6&7
SESSION 7 20th May 14:00 – 15:00	Increasing impact and sustainability	Elodie Pascal & Sylvia Burssens	How to choose and when to use what kind of indicators	Good experiences with use of quantitative and qualitative indicators	Read "The Thematic Network Explorer's Guide" chapter 6&7

4. Content / results

4.1. Kick-off webinar May 11th 2020 10:30 - 12:00: Guide to enter the online meeting, prerequisite for the upcoming workshops

11:00 – 12:00: session 1: Introduction to the "EURAKNOS Thematic Network Explorer's Guide"

Presenters: Ilse A. Rasmussen (AU/ICROFS) & Maxime Marois (IDELE)

Meeting Facilitators: Merete Studnitz (AU/ICROFS)

Participants: 48 participants attended the webinar, of which 21 were from EURAKNOS. Other participants included 3 advisors, 4 consultants, 3 farmers, 1 IT-professional, 1 policymaker, 15 researchers.

4.1.1. Aims/objectives

During this session, there was an introduction to the EURAKNOS TN and the aim of the workshop and the TN Explorer's Guide, the methodology of the workshops, and an explanation of the programme on May 18th, 19th, and 20th 2020. (See Annex III).

4.1.2. Methodology

At this first introductory webinar, all potential webinar participants were introduced to the EURAKNOS TN. To "break the ice", the first interactive exercise was to write ones' name and "Hello" in one's language using Mentimeter. That way, participants were also introduced to using Mentimeter, a polling system where participants by entering the website "menti.com" on their computer or smartphone and using a code shown in the presentation online can enter replies that are then shown on the screen for all participants to see. The next exercise/poll was that participants were asked to describe themselves in three words. This gave everyone an idea about the participants' profiles. Next, all were asked to reply whether they felt excited, nervous, and/or ready to learn for the first workshop.

There was then a short presentation of what TNs are and more specifically what the EURAKNOS TN is about so that everyone was at the same level.

‘Nervous’ was 2.2.

For the question at the end about how the participants found the webinar, 5 replied ‘super’, 30 ‘interesting’, 2 ‘confusing’ and none ‘Did not live up to my expectations’.

For the question about what was important, there was a diversity of replies, but there were some tendencies where more participants had replied similarly

- To get a description of EURAKNOS and its aims
- To get an overview and purpose of the webinar series
- To understand expectations to the participants before the next weeks’ webinars, including what to do for homework
- To help participants select which of the following sessions to participate in
- That the online meeting format worked well and made Europe smaller
- That the meeting was well prepared and facilitated
- That the interactive polls were fun
- That it was good to network e.g. with people that had met at the previous workshops/working group meetings
- That it was sad to miss lunch and networking together in vivo

To the question about how we could improve such an online webinar/workshop, examples of replies were:

- That it had been good including the facilitation
- That even more interactive work would be good
- To share the full list of participants
- To use another meeting tool than Zoom
- To use breakout rooms with fewer participants
- To share the materials during the webinar (instead of after)
- Avoid switching between presenters/screens

4.1.4. Outcome

After the kick-off webinar, the participants know more about EURAKNOS and the ‘TN Explorer’s Guide and what was expected of them in preparation for the rest of the webinar series. They have been introduced to the Zoom meeting tool as well as the Mentimeter poll tool.

4.2. Session 2 – May 18th 2020 10:00-11:00: The roles of different actors in the Multi Actor Approach in Thematic Networks.

Presenters: Elodie Pascal (presenter)(GLZ), Sylvia Burssens (facilitator) (UGent) & Laurens Van der Cruyssen (facilitator) (LFG).

Meeting Facilitators: Merete Studnitz & Ilse A. Rasmussen (AU/ICROFS)

Participants: 39 participants attended the webinar, of which 22 were from EURAKNOS. Other participants included 2 advisors, 4 consultants, 2 policymakers, 9 researchers.

4.2.1. Aims/objectives

The purpose of this session is validating the sections about the MAA in TN and to discuss the roles of the different actors in the MAA of TN’s. (See Annex III).

4.2.2. Methodology

Participants had to read the draft ‘TN Explorer’s Guide’ and follow the introductory session given on Day 1 (May 8th) after which they could inscribe for session 2 on the MAA on May 19th. In preparation for this session, they had to prepare answers to the questions that, during the webinar, session 2 were displayed by Mentimeter in the same order:

- 1) Is the principle of implementing an efficient MAA made clearer by reading the Guide?
- 2) What did you find in particular useful in the Guide regarding the implementation of an efficient MAA
- 3) If you did not find it useful: What important aspect of the implementation of an efficient MAA would you include in the Guide?
- 4) Is the principle of allocating roles and responsibilities amongst partners made clearer by reading the Guide?
- 5) What important aspect of the allocation of roles and responsibilities within the consortium of a TN/MAA project would you include in the Guide?
- 6) Are the suggestions about the facilitation activities and the profile drawn useful?
- 7) What other aspects of the MAA would you include in the Guide, if some important elements were missing according to you?
- 8) Based on your experience, what would you advise to the TN community to better evaluate impact (uptake of results) and sustainability of a TN?
- 9) Please give concrete examples of practices in TN/MAA projects that lead to a better evaluation of impact and sustainability

At first, there was an icebreaker ‘get to know each other’ exercise in which participants could give their name and mention if they were part of a thematic network and what their role is.

After, the questions of the homework were asked, and participants had to respond by use of the Mentimeter. In the second part of session 2, participants were divided into three groups (break-out rooms) and inquired about their experiences during different project-phases within a TN. Following questions were raised:

In the several break-out rooms questions about the TN's end-user journey were discussed

- 1) Were you involved during the conceptualisation phase?
- 2) Where you involved during the initialisation phase?
- 3) Were you involved during the execution phase
- 4) Were you involved during the post-execution phase

For each of these questions, the participants were asked to reflect over:

- a. If no, is there a specific reason for this? Would you have like to be involved during this phase?
- b. If yes, what are the challenges you experienced during this phase? What could be possible solutions to deal with these challenges?

For this session, two discussion groups were made for participants to give inputs on the different phases of the project, in particular, the initialization and execution phase (see Figure 3).

During the whole webinar, participants could use the chat function, ideas, and suggestions were also captured in the section on results, as well as personal contributions on specific items sent by mail after

the finalization of session 2 webinar.

The TN explorer's guide framework

Figure 3. The TN Explorer's Guide framework

4.2.3. Results

4.2.3.1 Who is here? (Mentimeter)

Participants present here had different backgrounds. Social scientists as well as agricultural engineers were present. Amongst other, links were indicated with TNs OK net Arable & OK-Net EcoFeed (n=1), CERERE (n=1), EUREKA (n=1), FAIRshare (n=1), FERTINNOWA (n=2), Hennovation (n=1), Inno4Grass (n=1), SmartProtect (n=1), Winetwork (n=2), Incredible (n=1), SKIN (n=1), and I2Connect (n=1) as well as with H2020 MAPs DISCONTTOOLS (n=1), LIAISON (n=2)..

4.2.3.2 The EURAKNOS Thematic Network Explorer's Guide (MAA Homework) (Mentimeter)

The majority of the participants agreed that implementing an efficient MAA was made clearer by reading the Guide (18 voted yes against 4 no).

On the question of what they found particularly useful, they highlighted the key ingredients, the clarity and the logic intervention to choose and involve the relevant actors at the onset of the project, the identification of their role, and way actors were involved on different levels and the different perspectives that need to be included by the core group to that extent. Also, the ways to meet end-user needs, improve their involvement in the project, as well as the knowledge pathways framework were found to contribute to better practice and impact for TNs.

On the questions of what important aspect of the implementation of an efficient MAA should be included, the way to detect and select appropriate actors to engage in the conceptualization phase would be useful, and also the way to influence the relationship of additional power of different actors amongst each other e.g. how to speed up scientists for practical useful knowledge, how to get more in-depth in the opinion of the advisor community? The Guide should be more tangible, with practical examples (e.g. face to face meetings, demonstrations, farm exhibitions, and farm visits, and links to existing TNs) and tools. It takes also time to hear the farmer's requests and listen to their needs. The first step of the Guide should help actors reflect 'why do you need to set up a TN consortium to implement your project idea – is the TN the right solution?'. The way to define the roles of actors and stakeholders during project implementation should be better highlighted, tools are needed to address the users' needs, identification of actors and stakeholders, and the relation between them and a feedback function for each of the actors. The criteria and conditions when the Guidelines apply or not should be clearer. It could help to include some examples of MAA that was not implemented well and give ideas on how to improve them.

There was also a suggestion to better distinguish "project" from "network" to make it more readable. Besides, the remark was made that the terminology of the pathway is not so well aligned with the EU terminology. Differences between an actor, stakeholder, and consortium should be better clarified.

Most of the participants believed that the principle of allocating roles and responsibilities was not sufficiently made clear (8 voted yes against 15 no).

On the question of what important aspects in support of roles and responsibilities within the consortium of a TN/MAA project would have to be included, it was marked that the Guide needs to better distinguish between the roles & responsibilities needed from a project perspective vs. network perspective, partner vs actor, actor vs stakeholder, and to highlight the co-creation of the allocation of roles and responsibilities at beginning of project (make a better definition of co-creation?). Additionally, the need to change the concept of 'beneficiary' or 'end-user' to key players; farmers, or others to change their situation in the TN was emphasized. The question was also asked how to organise the direct link and who can be intermediary. In the Guide, the need for a good communicator was mentioned, but also facilitators, the different types of roles of these key (and bridging) actors should be more clearly defined e.g. administration, knowledge exchange, and how to engage these (e.g. outside facilitators). It was also mentioned that it would be good to include governance structures to be updated at different time intervals throughout the project lifetime to deal with the difference of skills between partners and motivate them throughout the project's lifetime. There should be flexibility in budget allocation to the right actors with the right expertise after the project is granted.

Most of the participants thought of the facilitation activities and the profile drawn on the facilitator as useful (19 voted yes against 3 no).

On the question, if other aspects or important elements of the MAA were missing, some participants indicated that the EC expectations from a TN (e.g. speed to reach the deliverables) and more testimonies from TNs should be included. Furthermore, the need for a budget increase end-users' engagement and assessing their needs, and the language barriers were highlighted. The way how to start a TN, and how to choose the partners including practical problems that are encountered when including actors, is not very well explained. Additionally, it was suggested not to add more but remove some sections to shorten and improve the key sections 'Practical tips and tricks'. The emphasis in a TN is on the knowledge exchange, not the invention, as from the systems perspective.

Based on their experience, participants would advise the TN community that the time it takes to exchange knowledge in the conceptualisation phase is crucial and needs to be shared by all partners. Furthermore, end users' opinion needs to be asked at the onset and during the project by surveys and phone calls, to be able to better create and evaluate impact (uptake of results) as well as the sustainability of a TN. No additional comments were given when asked to provide concrete examples of practices in TN/MAA projects that lead to a better evaluation of impact and sustainability.

4.2.3.3 *The TN's end-user journey (discussion groups)*

The results combine the answers of the three break-out sessions and contributions per mail after the sessions had finished.

1) *Were you involved in the conceptualization phase of the project and which was your experience? If yes, how did it work out? If no, how do you think it could be done better to get more engagement?*

Arriving at the submission phase is already a big deal. Most of the time participants were not involved but would have liked to be involved. They also think it's hard to find people with experience on this and that there are two levels to be considered: 1) when the project is designed and 2) when the project is executed with the end-users.

A nice example of the conceptualization phase is in the I2connect project where partners had to take some time to design WPs, the first result was not satisfying so partners met in one place and spent time together, and subsequently a great advancement was made. Group dynamics are very important. All the key actors (the core group) were engaged. At the start of Sheepnet, the main topics of interest for the stakeholders were defined, in this way they could ensure full engagement. Stakeholders and end-users were contacted during the conceptualization phase. They were consulted through study meetings.

At the beginning of a project, the focus is on what to do and who to involve, later on, when it becomes more specific, you don't have all the answers up front. The main challenge is to make the project 'clean', write the proposal, and prepare the kick-off meeting, sometimes it is hard to transfer your knowledge to everyone (the content), and get the train moving. The process could be improved by scoping a seminar with all actors and stakeholders, the project has to be relevant for all of them, as e.g.. A value chain can become very different in different languages.

For the Smartprotect project, there was a thorough exercise at the beginning. The learnings were to take enough time to define all stakeholders and to define their role in the project. A scheme was made mentioning the dynamics between them in the WPS. On top of that, it was really useful to make a table with the different kinds of activities in the project and which actors were involved. It is a dynamic scheme that includes feedback mechanisms during the lifetime of the project so that consultations can be made with stakeholders during the project can be changed accordingly. Specifically, it is dynamic between the WPs and the way consultations are done to get feedback.

In the conceptualization phase of SKIN, representatives of farmers organizations, and others with direct connections with stakeholders were involved.

2) *How much time do you think you need in advance before the proposal submission, how long does the conceptualization phase take in your opinion?*

SKIN was a project with a very well-defined topic, 6-7 months before were needed to make the

concept.

TNs need to start well in advance. The selection of project partners should be based on how well they can engage partners. The core group of the project can be important to deliver the proposal, but it is also important that during this phase (6-7 months before the start of the project), all the partners need to conceptualize and arrive at the proposal all together otherwise it might be difficult to manage the proposal if you did not participate to the last step of the project proposal. How to build TNs on top of OG's? For the new programming period, this will be an easier task. The managing authorities are the EIP and the CAP strategic plan needs to be involved in this because of the implementation of the EIP – AGRI through OGs and H2020 projects needs to be facilitated. This will be more enabled through the new CAP.

3) *What is your user experience in the initialization phase of the project? How did you involve actors?*

FAIRshare makes use of user-cases to get different actors on board who are not necessarily involved in the consortium.

On the question of how to define actors, and stakeholders some participants indicated to prefer 'actors' over stakeholders. The terminology of actors versus stakeholder is clearly defined by the EU, but several definitions are depending which level you are looking at: consortium level or value chain level, In the AKIS they are all called actors. It is very hard to invite new actors with the expertise you only know in a thematic area (own network). There is a difference in content and consortium formation. The project has to be made clear to all, get things going, and learn to know every partner and their role. During the initialisation of project consortium, partners have to agree on and understand clearly the project's objectives, while stakeholders have to agree on their most pressing challenges (needs), how to mobilise them and keep them involved.

4) *Execution Phase:*

The difference in budget planning between Eastern and Western Europe is stressed; there is a need for detailed specifications. Budget planning is key and making sure that all partners understand their role, clear and right data is crucial.

It is important to explain very well the role of the partners and the goals; this is the task of the coordinator of the TN. Stakeholder fatigue is a problem, the coordinator can't manage everything, you have to trust the partners, and keep a good level of involvement. During the execution phase, the momentum has to be kept going. It is difficult to keep the balance between a co-creation approach and a top-down approach. Some partners are used to work by themselves, others wait for detailed orders before they start working.

The TN Explorer's Guide should be practical and simple with detailed examples and testimony of some TN coordinators and partners to make it more real and personal. The practical information and Guidelines should be very visible and fast to be interpreted. You should catch all information in the blink of an eye. Some sections don't give real Guidelines to set a TN which is perhaps one of the major challenges of each TN. We should have a small interactive platform at the EURAKNOS website, where everybody can continue to leave comments and share experiences

4.2.3.4 *What did you learn about this session (Mentimeter)*

The collective knowledge amongst participants in this meeting will help improve the TN Explorer's Guide. People who were involved in a TN from conceptualization onwards are lucky but also have a huge responsibility. Some TNs work better than others, a shared vision is important. All TNs are facing a similar challenge in conceptualisation, implementation, execution. Take enough time to define the MAA in the conceptual phase. Facilitating agents (e.g. Inno4Grass project) are a great tool. More actors need to be engaged early on, we need to consider the conceptualization very strongly. OGs can link to TNs via Managing Authorities.

Finally, the participants regretted to have not more time to exchange the different journey phases of a TN. Writing in Mentimeter takes time and some of the Mentimeter questions would be better to be reworded, are leading, worded in a way to get the answers wanted! But making an MA webinar was a good initiative to organize this workshop. It reduces the time for travel, and it is good to hear other experiences and share your own.

4.2.4. Conclusion and next steps

In conclusion, participants think that the Guide should contain more practical examples, tools, and testimonies of TNs. The term end-users should be more defined in the Guide when mentioning their involvement in a project consortium, e.g. is it the farmer, the farmer representative, or growers association? The conceptualization phase and engagement of different actors with clear roles is considered a key for the success of a TN and enough time (up to 6-7 months) should be dedicated to the engagement of different actors and stakeholders through scoping meetings to get everyone on the same line, respond to end-users needs and hence create impact. Key intermediaries to bridge or to facilitate can contribute a lot to this process. All TNs share a common vision and they all face the same challenges in the different phases of the project's lifetime. There is a need for a platform such as EURAKNOS to share experiences and exchange, and in this respect, this webinar was very useful.

Comments of the participants and main conclusions will be taken up in the next draft of the TN Explorer's Guide, more specifically on in the section on the MAA.

4.3. Session 3 – May 18th 2020 14:00-15:00: Assessing end-user needs and identifying the best ways to harvest and co-generate user-friendly knowledge

Presenters: Maxime Marois & Patrick Sarzeaud (IDELE).

Meeting Facilitators: Merete Studnitz & Ilse A. Rasmussen (AU/ICROFS)

Participants: 44 participants attended the webinar, of which 16 were from EURAKNOS. Other participants included 3 advisors, 2 consultants, 1 farmer, 1 IT-professional, 1 policymaker, 11 researchers, 1 SME; from 8 participants the background could not be identified.

4.3.1. Aims/objectives

This webinar-session was related to assess end-user needs and to identify the best ways to harvest and co-generate user-friendly knowledge. (See Annex III).

This webinar dealt with:

- In the first part, to know whether the TN Explorer’s Guide was clear and appropriated to the aim mentioned in the first pages. If important notions and aspects were missing. In this case, the participants were asked freely to contribute and share their suggestions.
- In the second part, to identify the needs of the end-users

The needs assessment aims to identify potential end-users. Within each category, there are many sub-categories with sometimes very different needs (e.g. digital skills, knowledge attractivity: practical versus theoretical, open-minded, network involvement...). The main question to be solved is: what do the end-users expect from TNs? How to evaluate the real needs of end-users? Is it a bottom-up approach (from the practitioners to the project consortium), a MAA to involve end-users as experts to express their needs in their daily fields of work and to test and approve solutions disseminated by TNs?

- In the last part, how to harvest and co-create user-friendly knowledge in a MAA which differs completely different from a top-down approach.

4.3.2. Methodology

Before attending this webinar session and in preparation for this session, participants received an explorer’s pack containing all the material they need to prepare themselves to contribute to the improvement of the TN Explorer’s Guide (see Annex I). Then participants were invited to read the TN Explorer’s Guide and also to prepare answers to the following questions:

First, some general questions related to the Guide were asked (about the purpose, the audience, and the utility):

1. How would you use the Explorer’s Guide?
 - Has the Explorer’s Guide made you reflect on the way your TN is/was working? (*If so, in what way? / If not, is there a specific reason for this?*)
2. How can we make the Explorer’s Guide more useful?
3. For who could the Explorer’s Guide be useful?
4. Which features do you need to properly present your TN and its activities on a digital platform for practitioners?

Secondly, some questions related to a specific chapter of the Guide which deals with the project execution and the implementation of the project activities

Following questions were asked:

1. Are we in phase between the assessment of user needs and the content that TN is likely to provide?
2. Regarding knowledge content, is it only necessary to focus on quality and maintenance issues?

General questions

1. Is there anything missing in this chapter?
2. Please provide any relevant examples for the good practices boxes

All the questions were addressed during the webinar in the form of participatory workshops that allowed participants to share their views and experiences.

This webinar session was alternating a short presentation (see Annex III) and collections of the opinions

of the participants as a TN expert and/or "knowledge users" by the way of participatory workshops.

The online participatory workshops were conducted by using the digital tool, MURAL. The use of this tool requires upstream preparation, which has consisted of:

- getting your hands on the tool, knowing the features,
- ensure that the tool is in line with our needs,
- prepare our presentation material
- identify the tools that will be proposed to the participants.

We chose to ask each participant a question and to collect their opinions by using coloured sticky notes that each expressed themselves in three areas related to the question asked, namely: comprehension, validation, and suggestion.

4.3.3. Results

4.3.3.1 *Who is here (Mentimeter)*

Participants present here had different backgrounds. Social scientists as well as agricultural engineers were present. Amongst other, links were indicated with TNs OK net Arable (n=3) & OK-Net EcoFeed (n=1), CERERE (n=1), EUREKA (n=4), FAIRshare (n=1), FERTINNOWA (n=1), Hennovation (n=1), Inno4Grass (n=1), SmartProtect (n=2), Winetwork (n=2), Incredible (n=1), SKIN (n=2), and I2Connect (n=2) as well as with H2020 MAPs DISCONTTOOLS (n=2), LIAISON (n=3). A representative from the TITRIS database project (Lithuania) was present (n=1).

4.3.3.2 *General feedbacks on the Explorer's Guide :*

An exercise was carried out using MURAL, an online tool that works much as a whiteboard or flipchart where all participants can add comments on virtual "sticky notes". This general assessment to evaluate the level of understanding of the participants after their first reading of the Explorer's Guide. We wanted to get their views on the Guide, to ask them about the purpose (is this Guide for you? How to use this Guide?) and to know if the recommendations and the Guidelines are sufficiently clear (what is still missing (inputs missing)? What are your suggestions?).

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA	COMPREHENSION	VALIDATION	SUGGESTION
<p>Guide format (length, balance between theoretical and practical input)</p>	<p>boxes with examples from practice are good</p> <p>The good examples make it easy to follow and relevant</p> <p>nice examples</p> <p>More practical Examples needed</p> <p>Good length and good balance but need more concrete examples</p> <p>easy to read</p> <p>easy to understand</p> <p>writing style is fine (easy to read and understand)</p> <p>Too theoretical, not enough practical. Needs more examples of methodologies and their pros and cons. E Mauri</p> <p>too long</p> <p>too much jargon</p> <p>too academic, too much like the EU existing guides</p> <p>some concepts could be a bit more clear</p> <p>lack of methodologies</p>	<p>good format</p> <p>good format</p> <p>lots of checks; describe a 'making of'</p> <p>method does not reflect limited time to pull together planned network</p> <p>Take out definitions and put these separately</p> <p>too academic</p>	<p>Add comic/visual graphics</p> <p>Guide is logical but does not reflect the timescales</p> <p>More detailed case studies for dissemination methods, what went wrong and how to fix it</p> <p>add more examples, testimonies from successful coordinators</p> <p>more checklists to summarise the texts</p> <p>Align the use of the pathways with the EU terminology from the work programme</p> <p>Use the document as guidelines to ask TN about examples on how each TN worked/solved/faced each issue. E Mauri</p> <p>more examples</p> <p>link to project basics: WPs Dets Tasks</p>
<p>Tailored to the target?</p>	<p>as a TN coordinator is OK, maybe not for all partners, especially practitioners</p> <p>not adapted to all stakeholders</p> <p>Maybe two different formats: one like this and one shorter version (you can send the right format to the right audience)</p> <p>Written for those that have some understanding of H2020 experience already</p>	<p>Make sure language appeals to the target group. The EC inspired jargon isn't always helping</p> <p>It's interesting to consider that for farmers end-users, farmers organisations or advisory services could play the role for dissemination</p> <p>the essence is link FG-TN-OG ; include that figure: many TN members meet in FGs they work for OGs, but the link to OGs is not easy, etc</p>	<p>more templates and e-tools for design and management</p>
<p>General remarks on the topics covered in the various chapters</p>	<p>End-users will adapt actions to their own specific context, not take it as a blueprint</p> <p>The structure and the topics are good. E Mauri</p> <p>target : TN coordinators or EU project coordinators but people still working in Multi-actor approach projects are less concerned because they know how to built such a group</p> <p>not all topics are represented.</p> <p>the budget for example, and how important it is to have budget for travel and stakeholders</p>	<p>More emphasis on the context where practices have worked and not worked. But honest</p> <p>have a template to link budgets, tasks deliverables per partner (model made for Fairshare ask me (peter)</p> <p>Concrete tools to organise workshop for dissemination and help end-user to exchange and keep back home knowledge</p>	<p>How to validate the information collected in the TN and choose which information to disseminate, which information is reliable ?</p> <p>deepen the definition of actors</p> <p>Communication tips for communicating with the commission</p> <p>idea on the timing of the activities and efforts needed</p> <p>how to motivate really the practitioners to participate in TN and to use the results afterwards</p> <p>important to provide enough money for people in charge of end-users dissemination</p>

Figure 4. One MURAL practical exercise of 10 minutes to get feedback, tips, examples on different topics related to the Guide

Our outcome:

4.3.3.3 A set of recommendations and opinions to be taken into account to improve the content and quality of the Guide

About the Guide: nice presentation (good length, attractive contents), the participants appreciated the fact that the Guide is a good mix between some practical and theoretical inputs but now a good balance must be founded. It is also necessary to add more relevant concrete examples.

Think about simplifying the speech to be better understood. Think about defining important concepts that recur regularly. The principle of adding checklists by key steps is interesting. Plan to add more feedback from previous TNs.

About the targets: targets are correctly defined and presented at the beginning of the Guide. Be clearer in specifying who the Guide is aimed at, as there is a lack of understanding about the targets of the Guide. It is primarily addressed to the coordinators.

About the Guide's topics: some participants would like the content of the Guide to go even further to address very practical topics (such as budget steering, time management, project management...) or the involvement of practitioners as end-users.

4.3.3.4 Needs assessment

One MURAL practical exercise of 15 minutes, to get feedback and inputs from participants on “What are the main end-users’ characteristics to take into account to provide them the most relevant content?”.

Our outcome:

Farmer and forester categorization: knowledge ready for use. Approved knowledge: they are expecting approved and very practical solutions. Very important to involve practitioners from the beginning of the project until the end, to be sure to tackle their expectations.

Advisor categorization: key actor in knowledge transfer between science and field. Often it's the resource people to get the knowledge to farmers. Be careful about the language: translate in the native language is very useful.

An even more appropriate and effective solution would be to set up farmer-adviser pairs to associate them in this process of co-constructing a knowledge reservoir.

Teacher categorization: they probably expect some educational materials.

4.3.3.5 Knowledge management

One MURAL practical exercise of 15 minutes, to get feedback and inputs from participants on “the knowledge management: the key steps of the process”.

Our outcome:

The key steps of knowledge management are:

Collect: More concrete examples are expected, notably on the presentation of useful tools to collect the needs of end-users. It is important to insist on the different sources of knowledge that exist and that are available, not only what is written in the bibliography, but also to think about including and disseminating good practices from the field that are properly documented.

Co-generation: some relevant are expected in the Explorer’s Guide to present some previous initiatives between scientists and practitioners working in closed collaboration for sharing knowledge.

Translate: Emphasize the different channels of dissemination that exist, trying to weigh the advantages and disadvantages. It is obvious that it is necessary to be able to use the most appropriate ones, but also to be careful to use different channels to reach different audiences and thus reach as many end-users as possible.

4.3.4. Conclusion and next steps

In conclusion, participants think that the Guide should contain more practical examples, tools, and testimonies of TNs.

The participants appreciated the multi-actor approach that runs throughout the Explorer’s Guide. It might be the best way to collect understandable knowledge for “knowledge users”, to set up a HIKR, and to translate in the most appropriate format for end-users as practitioners.

All the TNs share the same concerns and difficulties to solve. The availability of a Guide that can provide some Guidelines, thus saving time and benefiting from shared previous experiences and good practices is much appreciated by participants who do not want mistakes made to be repeated.

Comments of the participants and main conclusions will be taken up in the next draft of the TN Explorer’s Guide.

4.4. Session 4 – May 19th 2020 10:00-11:00: Designing your end-user engagement strategy

Presenters: Jessica Stokes (presenter) & Lisa Williams van Dijk (facilitator) (RAU).

Meeting Facilitators: Merete Studnitz & Ilse A. Rasmussen (AU/ICROFS)

Participants: 35 participants attended the webinar, of which 17 were from EURAKNOS. Other participants included 3 advisors, 2 consultant, 2 policymakers, and 11 researchers.

4.4.1. Aims/objectives

The main aims of this session for EURAKNOS were twofold: to gain feedback on the structure and content of the TN knowledge pathways framework, and validate its fit for purpose by gathering best practice examples from within existing participating TNs. The second aim was to gain general feedback and input on the content of the Explorer’s Guide for the sections on designing your end-user engagement strategy. An objective of this session for the end-users was to facilitate an engaging, participatory online webinar and learning experience for the participants. (See Annex III).

4.4.2. Methodology

Participants were introduced to the TN Explorer’s Guide in an introductory webinar session delivered on Monday 11th May (10-11 am), after which they were sent the Explorer’s Guide and given a week to read and reflect on the questions posed for Session 4, in preparation for the designated Session 4 webinar on Tuesday 19th May (10-11 am). In preparation for this session, participants were asked to

come prepared to answers the questions posed and input into the content and structure of the knowledge pathways framework. During session 4, Mentimeter was used to anonymously collate participant answers, while displaying the collective responses on the screen in real-time for everyone to see, learn, and reflect on. MURAL, a digital whiteboard tool that allows you to collaborate with remote participants was used to collect and display qualitative feedback from participants with regards to the content, structure, and best practices of TNs within the knowledge pathways framework, and designing your end-user engagement strategy. These digital tools were selected based on being the best like for comparison to delivering the workshop face to face. For example, MURAL is the equivalent online tool to how we would have run the session if we had been able to have everyone in the same room, using sticky notes to display and share collective ideas. Webinar participants were given the following instructions to come prepare for Session 4:

“Please read through TN Explorer's Guide sections 2.2, 4.4 and 4.5 and reflect on the following questions:

1. Does the knowledge pathways framework (page 13) help you to think, reflect, and identify the most effective strategies for your thematic networks (a)? Please explain in which ways this framework helps that process or not (b)? And if not, why not (c)?
2. As an exercise in applying and testing the pathways, can you think of a best practice example from your project experience which has utilised one or more of the pathways? Please come ready to discuss your example(s), explain the strategy behind it, as well as (estimated) impact.
3. In the dissemination section (page 28) the statement is made that it is important to ensure the best fit before best practice. To what extent do you agree or disagree with this statement (a)? Please explain why (b)?
4. Have you got any practical experience of multiplying and enhancing exploitation (page 29) for quick wins?
5. Is there anything missing in these specific sections?
6. Please identify any relevant examples for the good practices boxes in these sections.”

4.4.2.1 Webinar delivery

The webinar session was conducted via a secure link to a Zoom session where participants were admitted one by one after completion of a participant consent form. The functions available to the participants during the webinar included the chat function which participants were encouraged to use to pose questions and clarify understanding. Alternatively, they could ‘raise their hand’ and unmute their mic to speak. The presenter used a PowerPoint presentation to aid the session (link to PowerPoint), welcoming the participants, introducing herself, the facilitator, and the aims and objectives of Session 4 (see slides 1-4, 5 minutes) (all slides can be found in Annex III).

Mentimeter was then used to ‘break the ice’ and facilitate a quick introduction to everyone in the ‘room’ where participants were asked to share: ‘Who are we? Please tell us all your first name and in a few words sum up the skills you bring to this workshop’. As responses came up on the screen, the presenter read them out for all participants to hear.

Next, participants were introduced to the concept of the knowledge pathways framework (slide 5) and the questions of the homework were facilitated in the order presented above, using Mentimeter for questions 1 (slides 6-13, n = 23 (a), 32 (b), 19 (c), 10 minutes), 3 (slides 15-18, n = 19 (a), 22 (b)), and 4

(slides 19-20, n = 18, 10 minutes), and MURAL for questions 2 (slide 14, 15 minutes), 5 and 6 (see slide 21, 5 minutes). For the Mentimeter exercises, the presenter read out each contribution from participants as it appeared in real-time on the screen. For the 1st MURAL exercise (question 2), participants were given 10 minutes to work independently before the presenter read out highlight contributions from participants to consolidate the session, thank participants for their contributions, and drew the session to a close. During the execution of the webinar, as the presenter valued keeping to time and having ample time to gather participant feedback, there were only 5 minutes to complete the 2nd MURAL exercise (questions 5 and 6); however, both MURAL exercises were kept open until the end of the following week (10 days) to allow participants to add more input(s) at their convenience.

The last section of the webinar was an opportunity for participants to ask questions (slide 21) and for the team to gain feedback and an evaluation of the participant's satisfaction (slides 22-27, 10 minutes). Here participants were asked to:

1. Describe this session in one word (slide 24, n = 28)
2. To what extent were you about to share the feedback you prepared during the homework? (slide 25, n = 14)
3. Has this session made you think more about your current and future TN strategy? (slide 26, n = 14)
4. In what ways (if any) has this session helped? (slide 22-7, n = 12)

The participants were finally thanked for their time and valuable input, told they would receive a copy of the TN Explorer's Guide once it was finalised, and the webinar was drawn to a close

4.4.3. Results

4.4.3.1 *Who are we? Please tell us all your first names and in a few words sum up the skills you bring to this workshop*

35 participants attended the webinar, made up of agricultural researchers, social scientists, advisors, consultants, policy makers, facilitators and coordinators of existing TNs, as follows: EURAKNOS (n = 17), INCREDIBLE TN (n= 2), SheepNet (n=1), EUPig (n=1), Newbie (n=2), SKIN (n=1), OK NET ARABLE (n=1), CERERE (n = 1), Organic PLUS (n=1), Agrispin (n=1), PLAID (n=1) Roadmap (n = 1), NEFERTITI (n=1) DESIRA (n = 1), FERTINNOWA (n=1), FAIRshare (n=1), and Legumes Translated (n=1), as well as communication and dissemination experts (n = 2).

4.4.3.2 Does the knowledge pathways framework help you to think, reflect, and identify the most effective strategies for thematic networks?

23 participants answered this question (see slide 6). The majority of participants either completely agreed or agreed to some degree, as follows: 7 participants answered ‘yes’, 15 answered ‘to some degree’ and 1 participant answered ‘no’.

4.4.3.3 Please explain in which ways(s) this framework helps this process?

32 participants answered this question (for raw output see slides 7-10). The value of the knowledge pathways framework centred on providing a structured, step by step process approach to target end-users, by understanding and utilising existing and potential relationships within the thematic network and beyond. Highlighting quotes to summarise the value of the knowledge pathways framework to webinar participants included:

‘It shows the power of networks for knowledge transfer’

‘It provides a standardised approach where each pathway presents a different target group’

‘It shows the relationships between actors and how to communicate, dissemination and thereby increase exploitation (of knowledge)’

‘It splits the process by managing outcomes, giving helpful examples, e.g. “on-farm demos.”

‘As a checklist of different ways to disseminate knowledge: use as many as possible to reach more end users.’

4.4.3.4 Please explain in which way(s) this framework does not help this process?

19 participants answered this question (for raw output see slides 11-13). The key areas for improvement identified by participants centred around the framework in its current form were too generic and simplistic, more detail was required, and that the process is not linear but more interactive:

‘Too generic. The process of co-creation is more complex. More example should be provided’

‘The process is not linear, show it interactive/circular’

‘Gives more details how to implement each pathway’

4.4.3.5 As an exercise in applying and testing the pathways, can you think of a best practice example from your project experience which has utilised one or more of the pathways? And what is missing from the explanatory text?

In MURAL, for pathway 1, participants added 14 suggestions with regards to additional information required in the explanatory text for the knowledge pathways framework, 8 best practice examples, and 1 suggestion regarding the design of pathway 1. For pathway 2, participants added 5 suggestions to add clarity to the explanatory text, and a significant 20 best practice examples. For pathway 3, participants added 9 additions to better explain the knowledge pathways framework, and 27 best practice examples (see Annex III).

4.4.3.6 In the dissemination section of the Explorer’s Guide, the statement is made that it is important to ensure the best fit before best practice. To what extent do you agree or disagree with this statement?

A total of 19 participants answered this question, averaging 3.7 on a 6-point scale from strongly disagree (0) to strongly agree (5) (see slide 15).

4.4.3.7 Please explain why you agree or disagree with this statement?

A total of 22 responses were given to this question. For example, at the agreed end ‘best fit survives’ and ‘best practice has to be adapted to the context’, and at the disagree end ‘sometimes the best fit isn't quite good enough and we have to inspire using best practice to challenge people to progress.’ ‘We need to showcase what is possible, to inspire and move forward.’ For the full raw output, please see slides 16-18.

4.4.3.8 Have you got any practical experience of multiplying and enhancing exploitation for quick wins?

A total of 18 responses were given to this question (raw output slides 19-20). Some highlight responses included ‘Use of "flagship"/"ambassador" practices or impacts to motivate and give visibility,’ ‘use existing and trusted means of communication,’ ‘International exchange visits for advisors’, and ‘Engage policymakers! If something becomes a rule, then people have to comply.’

4.4.3.9 What is missing from sections 2.2, 4.4, and 4.5 of the Explorer's Guide? Please add your best practice examples.

Participants were shown the MURAL whiteboard to add their input; however, we only had 5 minutes for this exercise so input during the webinar was more time-limited than the 1st MURAL exercise. However, there were 33 suggestions made by participants. These focussed mainly on the need for more clarity and detailed explanation of the outcomes, recommendations, and tools made in the text, more practical examples to bring the theoretical frameworks alive; and more showcasing of existing best practices from past and current thematic networks. The full raw output from MURAL can be found in Annex III.

4.4.3.10 Do you have any questions for us?

Participants were able to ask questions throughout the webinar which the facilitator (Lisa) responded to, or where pertinent raised for discussion in this session. Questions on chat throughout the webinar included clarification on the arrows used and the levels of intimacy within the knowledge pathways framework, how long the MURAL activities will be open for input, clarification on what was expected within the MURAL activity, and discussion around the preference for the knowledge pathways framework to be presented as a circular rather than linear process. It was also articulated through the chat that this Guide should be available in several languages to increase its accessibility, reach, and impact. Finally, several participants articulated it would be good to have a slightly longer webinar, perhaps 1.5 hours, so there is time for more discussion.

4.4.4. Evaluation of the workshop

4.4.4.1 Please describe this session in one word (n = 28)

Figure 5. One-word descriptions of session 4 by participants.

4.4.4.2 To what were you able to share the feedback you prepared during the homework?

14 participants gave their feedback to this evaluation question, where 10 participants felt they could partially share the feedback they had prepared during the homework, and 4 participants felt they could fully share their feedback.

4.4.4.3 Has this session helped you think more about your current and future TN strategy?

14 participants gave their feedback to this evaluation question, where 6 participants felt 'not really,' 5 participants responded 'to some extent,' and 3 participants responded 'yes completely.'

4.4.4.4 In what ways (if any) has this session helped?

12 participants gave responses to this free choice question, stating the session had helped in the following ways:

1. A better understanding of the Explorer's Guide
2. Provide feedback and insights to improve the Guide (n = 3)
3. Highlighted different aspects of TN
4. The good thing about this session is that you focus on one area of the Guide
5. Hear what others are thinking
6. To see how you have used the different tools
7. Inspiration by others
8. Helps to rethink the TN I am involved
9. Liked the MURAL
10. Interaction has helped co-produce a useful Guide, the openness of presenters is refreshing
11. Sharing views

Within the answers to this question, some suggestions were also made:

1. It's difficult to think, write and register what the other participants say, in particular when the session is not in your usual language
2. Would have helped to have more verbal discussion with participants

4.4.5. Conclusion, outcomes and next steps

In conclusion, participants felt that the knowledge pathways framework was an added value to TNs as a means of cross-checking and utilising all available communication, dissemination, and exploitation pathways to end-users within and outside their TN, leveraging maximise impact. Participants preferred the original presentation of the knowledge pathways framework, described as ‘the egg of intimacy’ and could be presented in a Venn diagram to illustrate the interactive nature of each pathway and the lessening level of intimacy of knowledge creation as dissemination and exploitation move away from pathway 1, into pathway 2 and 3. The webinar was of most value to the authors of this section of the Explorer’s Guide, in validating the pathways with best practice examples to bring the practical recommendations to life. These sections of the Guide will be further improved based on the feedback from participants on the clarity of language and the need for more detail in describing the knowledge pathways framework. It was also suggested that to market the Guide widely, the inclusion of testimonials from enthusiastic advocates would act as influencers, as well as the need to consider translating the Guide into as many languages as possible to further increase its reach and impact across Europe and beyond. All input from the participants will be considered in the next draft of the TN Explorer’s Guide before final input and validation by our Strategic Innovation Board.

4.5. Session 5 – May 19th, 2020 14:00-15:00: Improving the common format of practice abstract

Presenters: Lisa Williams van Dijk (presenter) & Jessica Stokes (facilitator) (Royal Agricultural University).

Meeting Facilitators: Merete Studnitz & Ilse A. Rasmussen (AU/ICROFS)

Participants: 31 participants attended the webinar, of which 17 were from EURAKNOS. Other participants included 2 advisors, 1 consultant, 1 policymaker and 10 researchers.

4.5.1. Aims and objectives

All Horizon 2020 MA projects and TNs as well as all EIP-AGRI OGs use the common format to provide farmers, foresters, advisers, or whoever is interested in short and concise practical information. Links to audio-visual material (photos, films, etc.) are included as much as possible. The use of the EIP-AGRI common format should not only facilitate the exchange of knowledge, but also the contact between potential partners in innovation projects. The purpose is to contribute to building up a unique repository of practical knowledge across the EU via the EIP-AGRI project database which supports the dissemination of results of all interactive innovation projects. The writing of practice abstracts (PA) is obligatory and there is general conscientious amongst PA creators that they could become more practical. How can the current format be improved? The purpose of this session was therefore to provide recommendations and propose a new EIP-AGRI common format for Practice Abstracts based on the recommendations of past and existing thematic networks. (See Annex III).

4.5.2. Methodology

Participants were introduced to the TN Explorer's Guide in an introductory webinar session delivered on Monday 11th May (10-11 am), after which they were sent the Explorer's Guide and given a week to read and reflect on the questions posed for Session 5, in preparation for the designated Session 5 webinar on Tuesday 18th May (2-3 pm). In preparation for this session, participants were asked to read a prepared document explaining the purpose and layout of current PAs (see Annex I). During session 5, Mentimeter was used to anonymously collate participant answers, while displaying the collective responses on the screen in real-time for everyone to see, learn, and reflect on. MURAL, a digital whiteboard tool that allows you to collaborate with remote participants was used to collect and display qualitative feedback from participants with regards to the content, structure, and design ideas of participants about two scenarios presented for future PAs: an improved or enhanced format. Mentimeter and MURAL were selected based on being the best like for comparison to delivering the workshop face to face. For example, MURAL is the equivalent online tool to how we would have run the session if we had been able to have everyone in the same room, using sticky notes to brainstorm, display and share collective ideas, and move design ideas around to seek collective conscientious within the group. For the full preparatory material given to participants before session 5, please see Annex I.

4.5.3. Webinar delivery

The webinar session was conducted via a secure link to a Zoom session where participants were admitted one by one after completion of a participant consent form. The functions available to the participants during the webinar included the chat function which participants were encouraged to use to pose questions and clarify understanding, which the facilitator monitored and responded to. Alternatively, participants could 'raise their hand' and unmute their mic to speak. The presenter used a PowerPoint presentation to aid the session (link to PowerPoint), welcoming the participants, introducing herself, the facilitator, and the aims and objectives of Session 5 (see slides 1-3, 5 minutes) (all slides can be found in Annex III).

Since many of the same participants had been present in the morning session on end-user strategy a different icebreaker activity was used via Mentimeter (slides 4-6): why are you interested in this session about practice abstracts? This question was chosen to engage participants in the purpose of the session and facilitate the sharing of their motives. Participants were then asked via Mentimeter: how do they feel about today's session (slide 7).

The presenter then ran through the agenda for the webinar (slide 8) and asked if there were any questions. As a recap, the presenter then ran through the purpose of practice abstracts and the current use on the EIP-AGRI website (slides 9-10). The main section of the webinar was two interactive activities where participants were asked to submit their ideas and recommendations for improvement of the current PA format (see Annex III), followed by enhancement of the current PA format (see Annex III). The improved format consists of keeping PAs essentially, as they are however adding photos or links to practical videos etc. to increase the palatability of PAs. The enhanced format consists of changing the PA format whereby for example the information could be set out in a storyboard or social media platform. Both sessions were conducted via MURAL where participants had 10 minutes to input their ideas using sticky notes and the presenter consolidated each session by picking out themes and highlights from across the group's input and asking participants to verbally elaborate on their ideas.

The last section of the session shares the vision for future PAs within the EUREKA FarmBook²⁸. Participants were then asked if they had any questions or final comments to make, and the evaluation of the webinar was conducted via Mentimeter (see slides 15-20).

Mentimeter was then used to ‘break the ice’ and facilitate a quick introduction to everyone in the ‘room’ where participants were asked to share: ‘Who are we? Please tell us all your first name and in a few words sum up the skills you bring to this workshop’ (5 minutes). As responses came up on the screen, the presenter read them out for all participants to hear.

4.5.4. Results

4.5.4.1 Participants

Participants attended the webinar, made up of agricultural researchers, social scientists, advisors, consultants, policy makers, facilitators and coordinators of existing TNs, as follows: INCREDIBLE TN (n=2), SheepNet (n=1), EUPig (n=1), Newbie (n=2), SKIN (n=1), OK NET ARABLE (n=1), Organic PLUS (n=1), Agrispin (n=1), Roadmap (n = 1), NEFERTITI (n=1) DESIRA (n = 1), FERTINNOWA (n=1)

4.5.4.2 Why are you interested in this session about practice abstracts?

Twenty-three participants responded to this question (see slide 3-5 for raw output). The two main motivations were to create better uptake and use of PAs by making them more visible to end-users. Six participants felt the accessibility of PAs needed to be improved. For example: ‘If they are only the EIP knowledge hub, who will find them?’, ‘The EIP-AGRI is not a user-friendly website’ and ‘I would like to find out how we can make them being used.’ Fifteen participants believed that the format needs to be improved: ‘I would prefer them to be more dynamic and attractive’, ‘because they are not useful, as they are they are boring and are not used’ and ‘PA’s are such an integral part of TNs but they could be improved to be more useful to end-users.’

4.5.4.3 How do you feel about today’s session?

Twenty participants responded to this Mentimeter facilitated question. On a 6 point scale from strongly disagree (0) to strongly agree (5), participants reported being apprehensive (2.1) excited (3.7), and ready to participate (4.7) (see slide 7).

4.5.5. Improvement of the current format

Assuming the common format will be required in its current form, participants were asked to recommend improvements to increase its uptake and use, submitting their ideas together on a digital MURAL whiteboard (for the raw output see Annex II). The resulting recommendations are presented below:

4.5.5.1 Accessibility of information provided

1. Practice abstracts must be easily accessible to end-users and the EIP-AGRI website might not be the most obvious source of information for them.
2. Each PA should have a specific and real title related to the topic of the PA and this title should be noticeable.

²⁸ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qOr8nXN_xMQ

3. A proper search function is essential to provide a good/easy end-user experience and ability to filtering and sorting on the sector, topic, and language.
4. End-users are interested and searching for information/ innovations on a certain topic they can apply in practice. Direct access and potential full text/metadata search function for all PAs. All PAs should be accessible through their title and not 'hidden' after specific project information. Change accessible from: menu > find > projects to: menu > find > topics
5. Potentially connect PAs to search engines that end-users are already using and more visibility on these search engines.

4.5.5.2 Acceptability of information provided

6. End-users need the contextual information to be able to understand whether the information in the PA could be applied in their specific context. A section to explain the context or the character count should be increased to provide more contextual information.
7. Character count should be increased to provide more explanation of the actual practice promoted and the cost-benefit of uptake. Although requested in the current template the character limit is not enough to provide sufficient insight for an end-user to act.
8. Instead of the project coordinator, including the contact details of ones that developed and applied the innovation as the first-hand contact. The source of information needs to be clear - who developed this? As an end-user, you need to be able to judge whether the source is credible and trustable. Provide a clear link to the source of information.
9. What contextual information must be included? Country, farm type, rainfall, soils, supply chains.

4.5.5.3 Availability of the information provided

10. Many end-users across Europe do not speak English and having PAs in different languages is great. An opportunity to search by language is recommended - and potentially an option for automatic translation to extend the availability in different languages.
11. To support the limited character count it should be mandatory to provide an image/picture/illustration to engage the end-user, including links to videos and factsheets to inspire further exploration of the topic. Many links to maximise additional resources.
12. A practice abstract should provide a virtual bridge to further information such as factsheets, technical notes or videos on the topic developed by a specific project.

4.5.5.4 Quality of the information provided

13. A form of quality control on project level through limited peer review or editorial board with end-users should be employed. Engagement of end-users in the development of the PAs is essential in creating end-users friendly outputs. A clear process needs to be included in the PA guidance on how to do this.
14. A PA should directly link with a dissemination product produced in the project e.g. make them dual-purpose, and make a link to the dissemination output mandatory.
15. Balance quantity versus quality of the information in the PA.
16. Make sure style and tone are appropriate to the audience and ensure there is a quality control process.

4.5.6. Enhancement of the current format

In MURAL exercise two, scenario 2 was presented where extensive changes could be made to PAs. Participants were asked to imagine and submit ideas for how the PA could look like under this scenario. The resulting recommendation made built on the results for the improved version:

4.5.6.1 *Accessibility of information provided*

17. Dissemination of PA could be a newsletter sent by EIP-AGRI
18. The European Network for Rural Development (ENRD) suggests using 'hot topics' to categorise good practices. Something similar could be incorporated into PAs.
19. Use a format end-users are already familiar with
20. Make PAs more interactive and include a sharing or rating function and search function linked to the content in all relevant formats. E.g., you search sheep milking and you also get a link to a factsheet and video for instance.

4.5.6.2 *Acceptability of information provided*

21. An option for end-users to promote the practice abstract themselves via a sharing or rating function might provide some solution to this challenge as it provides credibility or validity through its value defined other end.

4.5.6.3 *Availability of the information provided*

22. Videos are a must. These are proof of what works. But short written descriptions are also needed.
23. Fact sheets rather than PA (add a link to examples). We should have a standard format for factsheets - just a page limit. Try to use existing resources from the project, not adding another layer of repeating the information.
24. To be effective you need short fact sheets (2 pages max) with videos, pictures, and schemes. A minimum single page of A4 and contains a short protocol context and cost-benefit analysis.
25. Fact sheets should contain some sections (practical use - economics - legal framework - these should answer the farmers' questions).
26. Fact sheets should contain links with more information e.g. videos, websites, knowledge reservoirs.
27. Change the format to pictures, video, and charts
28. Use results of a survey on the most used digital tools by farmers: i.e. videos are the most used. To reach farmers you need to have a video (could be coupled with a factsheet or toolbox) and a link in the YouTube description to the PA (not the other way around).
29. More farmer-friendly and should be focussing on changing behaviour, not just a task.
30. Toolboxes are practical and useful so what farmers need. Process descriptions are very important.

4.5.6.4 *Quality of the information provided*

31. End users should be involved in developing the format and validating the content.
32. I like descriptive information in a margin and main content in the body. The body of the PA should contain images, videos, etc.
33. Pictures, videos (under 30 seconds), and charts over large sections of text. It is important to break text down into short concise messages and sections.

4.5.7. Conclusions, outcomes and next steps

In conclusion, participants had a plethora of recommendations for both the improvement of the current format of PAs, as well as the enhancement scenario. Both the visibility and the content of PAs were recommended to be improved or enhanced, to make PAs both more visible, palatable, and therefore more impactful to end-users and stakeholders who support end-users. In both the improved and enhanced version of PAs, thematic networks want PAs to include far more visual content, and more dynamic interactive features such as a rating feature for likes and dislikes, which would enable end-users to vote the PAs up or down in popularity on a page and the site could use these ratings to feature PAs, integrating an end-user validation feedback loop for PAs. All the recommendations that came out of this webinar will be put forward to the EC as part of the deliverable 3.3, together with recommendations that came out of a previous face to face workshop with communication and dissemination experts. Besides, several recommendations were made for the integration of PAs into the EUREKA FarmBook which will be taken forward by this project with regards to the FarmBook design.

4.6. Session 6 – May 20th, 2020 10:00-11:00: Design and strategy of the future database and how TNs can present themselves on the digital platform

Presenters: Laurens Van der Cruyssen (LFG) & Davino Van Hall (LFG) & Hercules Panoutsopoulos (AUA).

Meeting Facilitators: Merete Studnitz & Ilse A. Rasmussen (AU/ICROFS)

Participants: The workshop's Session 6 was attended by 31 participants, 17 of whom were participants in EURAKNOS. Other webinar participants included 3 advisors, 1 consultant, 1 IT-professional, 2 policymakers, 6 researchers and 1 SME-representative.

4.6.1. Aims/objectives

Session 6 of the EURAKNOS online workshop was about the Design and strategy of the future database and how TNs can present themselves on the digital platform. The aims were to i) communicate, in a clear way, the EURAKNOS data model and how Thematic Networks can make use of the model to integrate data in a central database; and (ii) validate the learnings and assumptions on the added value of the EURAKNOS platform, how to present a TN on the EURAKNOS platform, and how to deliver a TN's output through the platform. (See Annex III).

4.6.2. Methodology

Participants who had followed the introductory session given on Day 1 (May 8th) could inscribe to session 6 on (a) **Design and strategy of the future database and** (b) **how TNs can present themselves on the digital platform**. The slides presented can be found in Annex III.

The first part of the session (section 1) was set up to be an elaborate presentation of all the work on the EURAKNOS database model. This would allow the participants to better grasp each element of the database model, the process of how it was constructed, and eventually provide feedback.

The second part of the session (section 2) was an interactive session to validate learnings & assumptions on (a) the added value of EURAKNOS platform, (b) how to present a TN on the platform,

(c) how to present a TN's output on the platform. In this section, we provided first some alternative directions to visual design to gather feedback. The rest of section 2 were open-ended questions to start a discussion. For session 6 we didn't divide into subgroups but discussed in the 'plenary'.

To gather feedback from the participants, we used a survey tool PollEverywhere – an alternative to Mentimeter, as an experiment.

The four pillars of the EURAKNOS HIKR design

Figure 6. Slide from the presentation showing the four pillars of the EURAKNOS High Impact Knowledge Reservoir (HIKR) as the basis for a common knowledge reservoir platform or e-KRP

The questions that were asked via Poll Everywhere were:

Section 1: Feedback on the database model

- 1) Do you believe that the technical design we've presented today already captures the core features of the output of your TN?
- 2) What pieces of information (i.e. metadata) would you like to be provided with when a digital output of a TN is being delivered to you?

Section 2: How to present TN output on the EURAKNOS platform

- 1) What are the benefits of adding your TN output to the EURAKNOS database
- 2) What are potential blockers for you to upload your TN output to the EURAKNOS database?
- 3) Which of 3 [presented] strategies would you prefer to collaborate with the EURAKNOS database?
- 4) In what way [of the presented formats] do you wish to represent your TN output in the EURAKNOS platform?
- 5) Which features of your current TN-website are most important to you?
- 6) Which of these [aforementioned] features would you rather 'outsource' to the EURAKNOS platform?

4.6.3. Results

4.6.3.1 *Who is here (Mentimeter)*

Participants attended the webinar, made up of agricultural researchers, social scientists, advisors, consultants, policy makers, facilitators and coordinators of existing TNs, as follows: INCREDIBLE TN (n=1), SheepNet (n=1), EUPig (n=1), SKIN (n=1), OK NET ARABLE (n=1), CERERE (n = 1), Agrispin (n=1), PLAID (n=1) Roadmap (n = 1), NEFERTITI (n=1) DESIRA (n = 1), FERTINNOWA (n=1), FAIRshare (n=1 as well as communication and dissemination experts (n = 1). A representative from the TITRIS database project (Lithuania) was present (n=1).

4.6.3.2 *Do you believe that the technical design we've presented today already captures the core features of the output of your TN? (PollEverywhere)*

Most participants agreed with the statement (74%); some had some additions (11%); some didn't know (16%). Nobody disagreed. The suggested additions to the database model were discussed in the group.

4.6.3.3 *What pieces of information (i.e. metadata) would you like to be provided with when a digital output of a TN is being delivered to you?*

Lots of examples were given, which could be segmented into broad categories: (a) key info about the data (i.e. title, author,...), (b) statistics (i.e. number of downloads), (c) content evaluation (i.e. maturity of the 'best practice').

4.6.3.4 *What are the benefits of adding your TN output to the EURAKNOS database?*

Participants communicated many benefits. The highest-ranking was (a) one place to find information in a common open-access database (N=7), (b) reaching a wider audience (N=4), (c) sustainability of the output of a TN (N=4).

4.6.3.5 *What are potential blockers for you to upload your TN output to the EURAKNOS database?*

Most common blockers stated were related to having to rework the data & metadata: (a) Having data in proper format & (re-)work on the metadata of the outputs (N=7), (b) Time and resources - may need adaptations in the future (N=4).

4.6.3.6 *Which of 3 [presented] strategies would you prefer to collaborate with the EURAKNOS database?*

Three strategies were presented. Nobody voted for option (a) Have no connection whatsoever with the EURAKNOS database. Options (b) store my TN output in my knowledge reservoir, but use the EURAKNOS database model, so EURAKNOS could more easily integrate my data later on & (c) store my TN output in the EURAKNOS database, and connect to the EURAKNOS API to show my data on my TN platform got an almost even distribution – respectively 47% & 53%.

4.6.3.7 *In what way [of the presented formats] do you wish to represent your TN output in the EURAKNOS platform?*

Among the presented formats the distribution was evenly divided over 3 formats: (a) have a list of all TNs with a brief explanation & a link to the website of each TN (31%), (b) Have a full page about my TN (31%), (c) OTHER (31%). Participants who answered 'other' preferred a combination of the presented

formats.

4.6.3.8 *Which features of your current TN-website are most important to you?*

A long list of features was suggested. These suggestions were mostly related to either (a) website functionalities (i.e. visually attractive & engaging for end-users, good search function), or (b) specific output formats (i.e. best practice collections)

4.6.3.9 *Which of these [aforementioned] features would you rather 'outsource' to the EURAKNOS platform?*

The features participants would rather outsource to the EURAKNOS platform are: (a) database (N=8), (b) social media function to which stakeholders can interact online (N=2), Rating function for content (N=1), Mapping tool (N=1)

4.6.4. Conclusion and next steps

The workshop session was attended by 31 participants. It was a very interactive session, and it can be said that there was an interest in the work presented.

Section 1 focused on the presentation of the EURAKNOS data model. The aim of the presentation delivered was to provide the rationale behind this endeavor, as well as present the methodology employed and its steps together with its result (i.e. the data model).

The interest of the audience and the reactions elicited as a result of the data model's presentation can be manifested by the responses provided to the questions addressed to them during the presentation. As an example, we can mention the high rate at which the EURAKNOS data model has been said to be efficient in capturing TN-related data particularities. The number of responses given to the second question is also indicative of the audience's interest in the work presented.

The presentation included two questions aimed to be responded to by the participants. The first questions intended to elicit the responses of the audience whether the EURAKNOS model can successfully capture TN-related data object details. The second question was used to prompt the participants to provide their insights on what metadata should be made available for a TN data object (as information that a user can have access to when retrieving the data object from the EURAKNOS platform).

As a final remark (serving as the outcome of Section 1), it can be said that the feedback on the data model, by the workshop session participants, was positive and allows us to conclude that the EURAKNOS data model has been well received.

Section 2 was set up to validate learnings & assumptions on (a) the added value of the EURAKNOS platform, (b) how to present a TN on the platform, (c) how to present a TN's output on the platform. Most of these assumptions were validated. So these insights feedback directly to the future vision of the platform & development of the platform.

The fully interactive setup of section two, focusing on open questions via Poll Everywhere to start the discussion and elicit feedback was well received.

Overall feedback was positive. Multiple people stated that they found the presentation on the database model clear and stressed the importance of providing links between thematic Networks.

Next steps are:

- Communication & dissemination of the EURAKNOS database model
- Incorporating the insights into the future vision for EURAKNOS
- Incorporating the insights into the development of the prototype for EURAKNOS

4.7. Session 7 – May 20th, 2020 14:00-15:00: Increasing impact and sustainability

Presenters: Elodie Pascal (GLZ) & Sylvia Burssens (UGent).

Meeting Facilitators: Merete Studnitz & Ilse A. Rasmussen (AU/ICROFS)

Participants: 34 participants attended the webinar, of which 17 were from EURAKNOS. Other participants included 3 advisors, 4 consultants, 1 policymaker, 9 researchers, 1 SME-representative; from 7 participants the background could be not identified.

4.7.1. Aims/objectives

Session 7 of the EURAKNOS online workshop was on the Impact and Sustainability of TNs. The aims of this specific session was to i) exchange good practices on impact and sustainability (ii) validate the learnings and assumptions of TNs on impact and sustainability (iii) define gaps in the TN Explorer's Guide Chapter 5 on impact and sustainability. (See Annex III).

4.7.2. Methodology

Participants had to read the draft TN Explorer's Guide and follow the introductory session given on Day 1 (May 11th) after which they could inscribe for session 7 on Impact and Sustainability on May 20th). In preparation for this session, they had to focus on Chapter 5 of the Guide, 'Increasing Impact and Sustainability', and think of what is missing.

An introductory presentation on Chapter 5 with the main Guidelines on impact and sustainability and different phases on the project was shared (see Annex III) after a short introductory 'get to know each other' exercise. Participants could give their name and mention if they were part of a TN, what their role is/and why they were participating. In the first part of the webinar, participants were allowed to comment on Chapter 5 through sticky notes using the MURAL tool. They were also asked to provide good practice boxes to illustrate the Guide and as a means to illustrate the Guidelines on impact and sustainability and fill potential gaps.

In the second part of the webinar session 7, the following questions were asked by using the Mentimeter tool:

- 1) How do you measure the short-term impact of your project? Please give concrete examples if possible.
- 2) Do you think it is relevant to allocate time for monitoring the (short-term) impact?
- 3) If yes, how do you allocate budget in the project proposal for monitoring the short-term impact?
- 4) Do you think it is relevant to allocate time for monitoring the (short-term) impact?

- 5) From your experience, how much additional time is needed for self-monitoring the impact during the MAA project/TN lifetime?
- 6) Based on your experience, which other activities might boost TNs' impact and make its results more sustainable?
- 7) How do you make your Thematic network sustainable after the completion of the project?
- 8) How do you make your TN outputs sustainable after the completion of the project?

Up till one week after the session participants could add on the MURAL exercise on Chapter 5 and/or by mail. Results also take into account the comments that were recorded in the chat during the webinar.

4.7.3. Results

4.7.3.1 *Who is here? (Mentimeter)*

Participants attended the webinar, made up of agricultural researchers, social scientists, advisors, consultants, policy makers, facilitators and coordinators of existing TNs, as follows: INCREDIBLE (n=1), EUREKA (n=6), EUPiG (n=2), NEWBIE (n=1), OK-Arable Net (n=1), CORE-ORGANIC (n=3), 4D4F (n=2), Organic PLUS (n=2), CERERE (n=2), DESIRA (n=2), Roadmap (n=2) and NEFERTITI (n=1).

4.7.3.2 *The EURAKNOS Thematic Network Explorer's Guide (Impact and Sustainability Homework) (MURAL)*

The results in the MURAL exercise can be found in Annex III.

Comments and feedback regarded the following aspects:

- The concept of impact should be introduced earlier in the Guide and should be better described.
- The differences among scenarios proposed at the end of the chapter are not entirely clear for the external users (e.g. definition of Knowledge Reservoirs).
- Examples of Indicators should be inserted to make it more concrete.
- The impact that many TN projects will aim to achieve is a change in farmer behavior, for example in adopting a new practice that the project promotes (Theory of change). Behavior change is multi-faceted and can rarely be traced back to a single event or point of interaction which makes it difficult to measure. Even more difficult if not impossible to measure in the context of a three-year project are societal impacts, such as environmental, social, or economic. Those that write TN applications sit with a difficult task of writing about impacts, hence they use the count clicks. Any thoughts that this Guide can provide to bridge this gap would be amazing and very useful. Besides, some extra pictures could support the message.

Participants were also questioning the meaning and added value of a figure in the Guide (see Figure 7 below) which is referring too much to a linear model.

Figure 7. Scenarios illustrating the potential contribution of the EURAKNOS data model and repository to future TN efforts.

When asked for good practice examples there were not many participants that made contributions.

Reference was given to:

- AHDB in the UK commissioned a review of social science evidence²⁹;
- Examples in the context of international development on how to use log frames to develop the objective, impact, and indicator framework³⁰. They are quite simple and useful.
- Projects and publications thereof on practice impact funded by the German Government in the field of Organic Farming Research^{31, 32, 33};
- Recent work on impact performed by Donal Murphy Bokern³⁴.

4.7.3.3 How to measure impact (Mentimeter)

Several ways to measure impact were indicated by the participants. These can rather be considered as proxy indicators as they do not measure the real uptake of the results as a major output of a TN.

- Metrics on communication and dissemination such as the number of website connections, number of Tweets, followers on Twitter and other social media, number of clicks and downloads, number of knowledge items or dissemination shared
- Involvement of stakeholder and number of participants at events/workshops/demonstrations
- Direct contact with and number of end-users during the project
- Cost/benefit analytics

³¹<https://ahdb.org.uk/knowledge-library/understand-how-to-influence-farmers-decision-making-behaviour>

³²<http://www.tools4dev.org/resources/logical-framework-logframe-template/>

³³<https://orgprints.org/30699/1/30699-12NA102-103-uni-kassel-wolf-2016-praxis-impact-II.pdf>

³⁴https://orgprints.org/36177/1/Beitrag_250_W01-07_Wissenschaft-innovativ-weiterdenken.pdf

³⁵<https://zenodo.org/record/1307947#.XtEQITpKg2w>

³⁵<https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regexpert/index.cfm?do=groupDetail.groupDetailDoc&id=36275&no=1>

It was perceived that the uptake of knowledge and practices is more difficult to measure. This can be done through:

- Evaluating events (e.g. through small surveys and feedback moments) and focus groups
- Mid-term surveys and reviews, testimonials
- Face to face meetings
- Direct feedback from people by phone calls or e.g. acceptance on scale 1-5 after a demo
- Metrics on communications: tweets, website visits, number of articles published, number of stakeholders registered, number of attendees in events

Participants highlighted the need for an impact framework with clear Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined at the start and to which reference can be made during the project. Short term impact should (also) be coupled to short term objectives of the project. The CORE Organic network has continuous monitoring of the activities from the start until the end and has set up a special monitoring group.

On the question of how to measure the impact of the TN as such was found to be critical. Observing how end-users interact with TNs materials (e.g. number of registrations to the TN newsletter and evaluation surveys) can be another way to measure the impact. To be able to raise impact TNs should also copy best practices from each other. Additionally, short evaluation questionnaire at the end of TN events, might allow to understand if participants had learned something. This could be followed up some months later by sending another short evaluation. Such surveys would have to be very brief but could give useful information on the real impact.

4.7.3.4 *Monitoring impact*

Most participants agreed asked that it is relevant to dedicate time to monitor the impact (18 voted yes against 1 no). When asked how much additional project lifetime is needed to monitor impact participants answered that half a pm would be needed regularly during the project (up to 6 pm during a project lifetime) at the condition that people are experienced with measuring impact and depending on what type of impact you want to monitor (e.g. short term versus long term). In any case, different cycles are needed to monitor impact. It depends also on the project and on the number of people who will be involved in measuring impact. In the CORE-Organic project, four people are continuously monitoring annually on a 2 pm basis. One participant suggested that the coordinator needs only 4 working days a year to do so and that each consortium partner needs 2 working days so that everybody is involved. It remains however difficult to motivate using time for monitoring impact because any estimations seem flimsy and lack value. A clear framework is needed. The budget is considered a priority to be able to dedicate time to monitoring the impact regularly.

4.7.3.5 *Impact and sustainability*

Activities that are considered to boost impact and make the TN more sustainable are:

- invest in follow-up initiatives based on the project outcomes,

- demonstration events with end-users (participating in international travel).
- reaching out to local and regional media,
- cross- exchange visits,
- connecting to end-user organizations to get increased visibility,
- continuous dissemination of the network results,
- full engagement of stakeholders, especially organizations and institutions

More specifically, the involvement of end-users, farmers, foresters, and advisors, at all stages of the project. Their engagement from the beginning and the connection to their networks, as well as training initiatives, can contribute to impact and sustainability. This key group of actors should be consulted continuously throughout the project about which output they need and how it should be organized and presented to create ownership. Consultations can be made in workshops and/or through involving a steering group. The engagement of national funding agencies ('national gatekeepers') is also essential to increase the sustainability of the network.

The impact should be put central in all activities, as each activity should contribute to creating impact. Besides, impact and sustainability can be enhanced by making use of existing platforms and collaboration with EURAKNOS to feed results within an open-source living knowledge reservoir (robust, searchable database for dissemination material such as practically oriented knowledge documents and videos). This will help to connect end-users and experts in Europe in an agriculture or forestry theme, link with national and regional organisations (e.g. NRNs and chambers of agriculture), the EIP-AGRI and other well-established networks with familiar and highly frequented websites, including educational systems. Sustainability of the networks is also important as a condition for several to get actors involved in the first place, especially farmers, already at the start of a project. A strong presence on social media is essential to keep the stakeholders connected and engaged. Tools to enhance impact and sustainability should be shared amongst the TN community so that follow-up projects can build on experiences of existing and previous TNs. The building of a self-sustaining and motivated TN community through the development of the common database is also important in that respect to ensure long term governance and continuity. An example is the Organic Farm Knowledge hub that was set up in a project and has since been used by several others. Having a TN website on an existing website instead of creating a new one should be considered. The 4D4F TN made use of an existing Flemish sensor database. For Organic PLUS, some results are placed on an existing French database (Biobase) and international database (Organic eprints)³⁸ with open access archives. In some cases, corepartners are committed to keeping the database alive. One of the main challenges is to convince an organisation to host an open-access database and regularly update it.

The topic of the TN and the types of output may also be an influencing factor, e.g. topics that are of broad societal relevance tend to stay longer alive, outputs that are rather linked to 'keeping the momentum' should not specifically be stored. Oplla³⁶ is a free life-long hosting platform. Results can also be stored in Zenodo³⁷.

Individual consortium partners can use outputs in their work streams and networks and as such act as multipliers of the dissemination of the results. In any case, a dedicated targeted dissemination plan is needed.

4.7.4. Conclusion and next steps

In conclusion, participants believe that impact and sustainability are strongly intertwined and are of utmost importance for TNs to be efficient. Sufficient budget and time in TNs should be allocated and to continuous impact monitoring during the lifetime of the project and also after the project. Engagement and co-ownership of stakeholders and actors, particularly end-user groups such as farmers, foresters, and advisors are key. Regular consultations can be done through workshops, surveys, face to face meetings, phone calls, or steering groups. Cross-exchange visits, demonstration events, study days, with strong involvement of farmers, foresters, and advisors, can contribute to achieving impact. Feedback loops should be provided in an impact framework based on KPIs that are being set at the beginning of the project but that can be adapted accordingly. There is a need to develop a standard framework that can be used as a model. The current indicators are mostly based on analytics of downloads, and the number of participants at events, and are, as such, rather proxy indicators than output indicators related to the practice and uptake of the results and knowledge collected and shared by TNs.

TNs should be able to build on each other and present their knowledge materials in databases. This is important to gain sustainability and hence long term impact. Partners may continue hosting or use can be made of existing databases at national, regional level, or platforms such as Zenodo and Oppla. Connection to existing networks and organisations are contributing to impact and sustainability as well as linking to educational institutions and training initiatives.

Most of the participants thought of the webinar as useful and are looking forward to following up on actions. Comments and major conclusions will be integrated into the TN Explorer's Guide, in Chapter 5.

4.8. Evaluation Workshops 11-20 May 2020

4.8.1. Aims/objectives

The evaluation aimed to get an impression of whether participants found the webinars satisfactory, whether they could use their homework preparations and whether the webinars were helping in their TN work. Besides, the organisers would like feedback to learn how to carry out such webinars better.

4.8.2. Methodology

In an email sent out after the end of the workshop, all participants were asked to evaluate the sessions in which they participated. The questions were for each of the sessions, they had participated in how the participants found the webinar, with the possible responses "super", "interesting", "confusing" and "Did not live up to my expectations" as well as "To what extent were you able to share the feedback you prepared during the homework in Session x?" with the possible replies "Fully", "Partially", or "Not at all". Another question was "Does the content of the session (not the Guide) help you in your current and future TN strategy?" where the possible replies were "Yes, a lot", "Yes, in part" or "No, not really". Also, it was possible to give free-text comments.

4.8.3. Results

Only 11 participants filled out the survey. The results can be found in Figure 8, Figure 9 and Figure 10.

Figure 8. Replies on the question: How was the webinar?

Figure 9. Replies on the question: To what extent were you able to share the feedback you prepared during the homework in the session?

Figure 10. Replies on the question: Does the content of the session help you in your current and future TN Strategy?

Since only about 20% of the participants have replied to the survey, the results should be interpreted with this in mind. Generally, most participants (that replied) either found the webinars super or interesting: 70 – 100 % of the participants replied this. 75-100 % of the participants found that they could share feedback about their homework in the sessions – interestingly 85 % stated this also for session 1, where there had been no homework to prepare! 67 – 75 % of the participants found that

the session they participated in, helped them in their current and future TN strategy, but this also means that 25-33 % replied “No, not really” and thus did not get input for their TN strategy.

The free text comments included many comments about interactivity: Mentimeter and MURAL made the sessions more interactive, but at times when e.g. many participants were working in MURAL at one time, it was confusing and difficult to follow. Some also commented that MURAL should have been introduced better, e.g. it did not work in Explorer, and not all could immediately figure out how to write on a post-it note. However, despite the interactivity, participants felt that it was difficult to have contact with the other participants. But still many felt that they got many good ideas from the sessions and the interactivity facilitated an exchange of thoughts. For many of the sessions, there were comments that time was too short and that e.g. 15 minutes more would have been beneficial. Several participants thanked the workshop and stated that they would use the experiences gained when conducting workshops themselves.

One comment we bring in full length: ‘it was an excellent session, well facilitated, with enough time left to people to think and write on the post-its. The mixture of MURAL, the Mentimeter, and direct discussion was very good. It felt like a face to face workshop’. This comment was for session 5, but the general direction of comments for all webinars support this.

One participant replied the same for all webinar sessions: ‘EU RUR15 CSA mandatory concepts and structures are not reflected, aiming results that are already ready for practice materialised as high TRL practical knowledge technologies + products + methods’. This comment is more for improvement of the TN Explorer’s Guide than an evaluation of the workshop.

5. General conclusion

The EURAKNOS workshop 2, originally planned to be conducted in April 2020 in Tallinn, Estonia, was due to the COVID-19 situation reorganised as a series of 7 online webinars held in May. In total, 70 people participated in one or more of the webinars.

The first webinar was a kick-off where participants got acquainted with EURAKNOS and the “TNs Explorer’s guide”.

Webinar 2 highlighted the importance of having a platform such as EURAKNOS to share experiences and exchange. Aspects related the MAA were discussed. Based on the outcomes of the webinar, the Guide has to focus on providing the following aspects:

- Make clear the way to detect and select appropriate actors to engage in the conceptualization phase.
- Describe tools to define roles of actors and stakeholders during the implementation phase (include testimonies from TNs).
- Make a clear definition between an actor, stakeholder, and consortium.
- Distinguish between the roles & responsibilities needed from a project perspective vs. network perspective.
- Make a clearer definition of co-creation.
- Need to change the concept of ‘beneficiary’ or ‘end-user’ to ‘key player’.
- The TN Explorer’s Guide should be practical and simple with detailed examples and testimony of some TN coordinators and partners to make it more real and personal.

Webinar 3 pointed out that since all TNs face the same problems, the guidelines that will be provided

in the “TNs Explorer’s Guide” will be very important and will allow to save time and use good practices derived from previous TN’s experiences. Based on the outcomes of the webinar, the Guide will have to focus on providing the following aspects:

- Find a balance between practical and theoretical inputs.
- Specify who the Guide is aimed at.
- Present previous initiatives between scientists and practitioners working in closed collaboration for sharing knowledge.
- Emphasize the different channels of dissemination that exist, trying to weigh the advantages and disadvantages.

Webinar 4 underlined the importance of the exchange pathways for cross-checking and utilising all available communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategies, leveraging the impact of a TN. Participants enriched the webinar with valuable examples that will be inserted in the Guide. They also brought up the language issues, encouraging EURAKNOS members to translate the Guide into as many language as possible to increase its impact across Europe. All input from the participants will be considered in the next draft of the TN Explorer’s Guide before final input and validation by the Strategic Innovation Board. Based on the outcomes of the webinar, the Guide will have to focus on providing the following aspects:

- Connection between the pathways should be highlighted.
- Provide more example regarding the co-creation process.

Webinar 5 discussed recommendations and a strategy to improve PAs. Special attention was given on how to increase the visibility and content to make them more impactful to end-users and stakeholders. All the recommendations, together with the outcomes of previous face-to-face workshops, will be put forward to the EC as part of the deliverable 3.3. Furthermore, these recommendation will be taken into account in the EUREKA FarmBook. Based on the outcomes of the webinar, the PAs will have to focus on providing the following aspects:

- Add visual contents, dynamic and interactive features (e.g. rating feature for likes and dislikes) to the PAs.
- Specific and real title related to the topic of the PA and this title should be noticeable.
- A proper search function is essential to provide a good/easy end-user experience.
- Include the contact details of ones that developed and applied the innovation as the first-hand contact.
- Opportunity to search by language is recommended.
- Balance quantity versus quality of the information.
- PAs should look like short fact sheets (2 pages max) with videos, pictures, and schemes.

Webinar 6 focused on the presentation of the EURAKNOS data model. Based on the outcomes of the webinar, the future digital platform where TNs will present themselves need to contain the following features:

- key info about the data (i.e. title, author,...).
- statistics (i.e. number of downloads).
- content evaluation (i.e. maturity of the ‘best practice’).
- visually attractive & engaging for end-users, good search function.

The EURAKNOS data model has been well received among participants. Insights and feedback to the future vision of the platform & development of the platform will be implemented during the next months.

The last webinar tackled the aspect of impact and sustainability in TNs.

- Participants agreed that budget and time in TNs should be allocated to monitor TNs impact also after their end.
- Engagements of actors, regular consultations, Cross-exchange visits can contribute to achieve impact.
- There is the need to develop a standard framework that can be used as a model to evaluate impact.
- Partners may continue hosting or use existing databases at national, regional level, or platforms such as Zenodo and Oppla.
- Connection to existing networks and organisations are contributing to impact and sustainability as well as linking to educational institutions and training initiatives.

Comments and major conclusions will be integrated into the TN Explorer’s Guide. Overall, participants gave a positive feedback and the EURAKNOS team had a lot of relevant feedback for the TN Explorer’s Guide, which has been revised accordingly and will be reported as D3.6.

6. Annex I

6.1. The Explorer's pack sent out to participants after the first webinar.

6.1.1. TN Explorer's Guide

For the TN Explorer's Guide we refer to D3.6 - HIKR Technical Guidelines.

6.1.2. Questions for homework

EURAKNOS

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs Towards
A European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

The explorer's guide

Questions for homework

You do NOT need to write answers to the questions, they are mainly meant to make you reflect and prepare for the sessions, you want to join. However, if you cannot join the session(s) to which you have inputs or if you have more to say after the session(s), we will be happy to receive your written answers or comments.

Please find question dedicated to session 4 at the last page of this document.

Name:

Affiliation:

General questions related to the guide (purpose, audience and use)

(For all sessions)

1. How would you use the explorer's guide?
2. Has the explorer's guide made you reflect on the way your TN is/was working?
 - *If so, in what way?*
 - *If not, is there a specific reason for this?*
3. How can we make the explorer's guide more useful?
4. For who could the explorer's guide be useful?
5. Which features do you need to properly present your TN and its activities on a digital platform for practitioners?

CHAPTER 2: MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH: ensuring end-user engagement

(For session 2 and 4 (section 2.2))

Specific questions

1. Is the implementation of an efficient MAA made easier by reading the guide?
2. Is the allocation of roles among partners made easier by reading the guide?
3. Are the tips about facilitation activities and the profile drawn for the facilitator useful?
4. What other aspects of the MAA would you include in the guide, if some important elements were missing according to you?

General questions

1. Is there anything missing in this chapter?
2. Please provide any relevant examples for the good practices boxes.

CHAPTER 3: WORKING EFFECTIVELY AS A MULTI-ACTOR NETWORK

(For session 2)

General questions

1. Is there anything missing in this chapter?
2. Please provide any relevant examples for the good practices boxes.

CHAPTER 4: PROJECT EXECUTION: implementing your project activities

(For session 3 and 4 (section 4.4 and 4.5))

Specific questions

1. Are we in phase between the assessment of user needs and the content that TN is likely to provide?
2. Regarding knowledge content, is it only necessary to focus on quality and maintenance issues?

General questions

1. Is there anything missing in this chapter?
2. Please provide any relevant examples for the good practices boxes

CHAPTER 5: MEASURING YOUR IMPACT AND TN SUSTAINABILITY

(For session 6 & 7)

General questions

1. Is there anything missing in this chapter?
2. Please provide any relevant examples for the good practices boxes

Questions for Session 4: Designing your end-user engagement strategy

(19th May 10:00-11:00)

Please read through TN explorer's guide sections 2.2, 4.4 and 4.5 and reflect on the following questions:

1. Does the knowledge pathways framework (page 13) help you to think, reflect, and identify the most effective strategies for your thematic networks? Please explain in which ways this framework helps that process or not? And if not, why not?
2. As an exercise in applying and testing the pathways, can you think of a best practice example from your project experience which has utilised one or more of the pathways? Please come ready to discuss your example(s), explain the strategy behind it, as well as (estimated) impact.
3. In the dissemination section (page 28) the statement is made that it is important to ensure the best fit before best practice. To what extent do you agree or disagree with this statement? Please explain why?
4. Have you got any practical experience of multiplying and enhancing exploitation (page 29) for quick wins?
5. Is there anything missing in these specific sections?
6. Please identify any relevant examples for the good practices boxes in these sections.

WORKSHOPS online

Kick-off 11th MAY

18th - 19th - 20th MAY 2020

Replacement for the workshop in Tallinn 27th, 28th, 29th April

EURAKNOS

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European Agricultural Knowledge
Innovation Open Source System

STEP 1: Kick-off webinar

Main objective: presentation of the 'EURAKNOS Explorers Guide'

Timetable: 11th May at 11 am CET (1 hour)

STEP 2: Individual 'homework'

Main objective: reading the 'EURAKNOS Explorers Guide'

Timetable: during the week beginning 11th May (2 - 3 hours)

STEP 3: Set of participative webinars

Main objective: presentation of the 'EURAKNOS Explorers Guide'

PROGRAMME FOR WEBINARS PRESENTING AND DISCUSSING EURAKNOS EXPLORERS GUIDE

Date and time and link	Topic	Presenter	YOUR outcome of participating	We wish from you	Preparation
11th May 10:30 - 12:00	GUIDE TO ENTER THE ONLINE MEETING prerequisite for the upcoming workshops		A smooth start of online meetings	Being on time	Computer and internet connection Headset A quiet room
SESSION 1 11th May 11:00 – 12:00	Introduction to the "EURAKNOS Explorers guide" Introduction to the methodology of the workshops. Explanation of how to choose between workshops next week.	Ilse A. Rasmussen & Maxime Marois	An overview of the guide on how to prepare and run a Thematic Network (TN)	Being aware Being open-minded	None
Homework	May 11 th to 18 th we kindly ask you to read "The Thematic Network Explorer's guide" now 30 pp, sorry - and prepare answers to specific questions. May 11 th you receive both EURAKNOS "The Thematic Network Explorer's guide" and the questions for your homework.				
SESSION 2 18th May 10:00 – 11:00	The roles of different actors in the Multi Actor Approach in Thematic Networks	Elodie Pascal & Sylvia Burssens & Laurens Van der Cruyssen	Who, When, How different actors are valuable to a TN	Participate in the discussion	Read "The Thematic Network Explorer's guide" chapter 2 & 3
Link for session 2: https://aarhusuniversity.zoom.us/meeting/register/u5MqceyoqTMrE9cNBINr1zBCjqPerVk3wod2					

SESSION 3 18th May 14:00 – 15:00	Assessing end-user needs and identifying the best ways to harvest and co-generate user-friendly knowledge	Maxime Marois & Patrick Sarzeud	Influence the EURAKNOS Explorers Guide regarding end-user needs	Your feedback to integrate in the guidelines for the future TNs	Read “The Thematic Network Explorer’s guide” chapter 4
Link for session 3: https://aarhusuniversity.zoom.us/meeting/register/u5wrd-uoqzMvGtBgA413Rwkqn2eqzwyRaDA9					
SESSION 4 19th May 10:00 – 11:00	Designing your end-user engagement strategy	Lisa Williams van Dijk & Jessica Stokes	How to validate the dissemination and exploitation pathways	Participation in surveys during the session	Read “The Thematic Network Explorer’s guide” Sections 2.2, 4.4 and 4.5
Link session 4: https://aarhusuniversity.zoom.us/meeting/register/u5AodumqqzG9Gzq0WvV0aJs9jnwutc7dv2					
SESSION 5 19th May 14:00 – 15:00	Improving the common format of practice abstract	Lisa Williams van Dijk & Jessica Stokes	Insight into different ways to disseminate	Your votes for different formats	Read “The Thematic Network Explorer’s guide” Please follow specific instructions for session 5.
Link session 5: https://aarhusuniversity.zoom.us/meeting/register/u5clcuiuqDgjH9SdeVWf0iMlxqzQseXa0Xf					
SESSION 6 20th May 10:00 – 11:30	Design and strategy of the future database and how TNs can present themselves on the digital platform	Laurens Van der Cruyssen & Davino Van Hall & Hercules Panoutsopoulos	Influence the EURAKNOS Explorers Guide regarding future database	Your input on how TNs want to present themselves on the platform.	Read “The Thematic Network Explorer’s guide” chapter 6&7
Link session 6: https://aarhusuniversity.zoom.us/meeting/register/u5wpc-isqj8iEtdhL9UZT5v327_cpEcw98Dz					
SESSION 7 20th May 14:00 – 15:00	Increasing impact and sustainability	Elodie Pascal & Sylvia Burssens	How to choose and when to use what kind of indicators	Good experiences with use of quantitative and qualitative indicators	Read “The Thematic Network Explorer’s guide” chapter 6&7
Link session 7: https://aarhusuniversity.zoom.us/meeting/register/u50pcumhrjkjEt3xx17HT-ceg7tKmp_G3Bpz					

	4 th June all participants will get a summary of all workshops and conclusions made from the workshops By the end of 2020, you will receive “The Thematic Network Explorer’s guide”
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6.1.4. Instructions for Session 5 - Practice Abstract

EURAKNOS workshop on the Thematic Network Explorer’s Guide.

Session 5: Improving the common format of practice abstract

19th May 14:00 – 15:00

The EIP-AGRI common format aims to facilitate knowledge flows on innovative and practice-oriented projects from the start until the end of the project and to provide farmers, foresters, advisers or whoever is interested with short and concise practical information in so called 'practice abstracts'. The These practice abstracts are a central tool to spread knowledge generated by TN and other H2020 interactive innovation projects. The EIP common format consists of a set of basic elements characterising the project and includes one (or more) practice abstract(s). And PAs *'will also give visibility to actors involved and enable measuring impact and rewarding of researchers' work for practice, in an analogue approach to research abstracts in peer reviewed journals*¹.

Practice Abstract format

Essential elements:

- **Objective of the project in native language and English:** what problems/opportunities does the project address that are relevant for the practitioner/end-user, and how will they be solved? - (300-600 characters, word count – no spaces)
- **Short summary for practitioners in native language and English on the (final or expected) outcomes** (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). This summary should at least contain the the main results/outcomes of the activity (expected or final) and the main practical recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

Recommended elements:

- **Description of project activities in native language and English:** (max 600 characters, word count – no spaces): short summary highlighting main project activities.
- **Short summary for practitioners in English:** short summary according to guidance (see box above under "practice abstract"; 1000-1500 characters, word count - no spaces)
- **Audiovisual material** which is useful and attractive for practitioners (e.g. YouTube link, videos, other dissemination material)
- **Website of the project (URL)**
- Links to other website(s) hosting information on the project (results) that are available after the project has ended, by preference using the existing local/regional/national communication channels that practitioners most often use.

Although the common format has been designed to be easily accessible online, understandable and applicable to the target end-users, it became evident from WP 2 and the discussions in with TN practitioners and end-users that this is not always the case. The main concerns related to the intended target group and the accessibility, acceptability, availability and quality of the information provided availability.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/sites/agri-eip/files/eip_common_format_-_14_oct_2015.pdf

Since the introduction of the common format with the PAs there has been a debate about the intended target audience. From the discussions there was a clear view that role of the advisor is to help farmers to utilize the information in the practice abstracts, hence potential more focus on promoting the use of these by advisor might increase its impact as well as providing some sort of support and guidance for advisors on how to use the information.

Accessibility of information provided: Practice abstracts must be easily accessible to end-users and the EIP-AGRI website might not be the most obvious source of information for them. A proper search function is essential to provide a good/easy end-user experience and ability to a filtering and sorting on sector, topic and language. It also needs to be noted that many end-users simply do not access the internet for information due to various reasons from actual limited availability, hence, will not have access to the information provided.

Acceptability of information provided: It is well known that one of the key factors for uptake and use

of information by farmers/foresters is trust in the source of information. The information provided in a PA needs to provide enough insight and potential 'evidence' that the source is credible (otherwise it will be seen as a risk). The information provided to be able to judge by an end-user whether the source is credible is currently very limited and often the source is unclear. An option for end-users to promote the practice abstract themselves via a sharing or rating function might provide some solution to this challenge as it provides credibility or validity through its value defined other end-users

Availability of the information provided: One of the main limitations is the availability of information in terms of language; many end-users across Europe do not speak English and limited content might also reduce its effectiveness of the action or outcomes being taken up by the end-user. In the current format with the character limited a practice abstracts cannot provide all of the information about a concept, approach or innovation but they must provide enough information to promote further enquiry, thus being a source of inspiration. They should also be a virtual bridge to further information such as factsheets, technical note or videos. This should not be optional but mandatory.

Quality of the information provided: There is currently no mechanism in place to ensure the quality of content in terms of the quality of language style, tone appropriate to the audience, clarity of description etc. as well as the quality of it (technical) content.

Taking the AAAQ criteria into consideration several scenarios can be developed. These scenarios look at:

1. Improvement of the current format. Assuming the common format will be required in its current format, what improvement could be made to increase its uptake and use? For example, at a minimum a better search function and mandatory links to information such as factsheets, technical note or videos

2. Enhancement of the current format. If more extensive change could be made how would the PA look like? For example, exploring the options for making it more interactive and including a sharing or rating function and a change in form to pictures, videos (under 30 seconds) and charts over large sections of text. There are already several TN who have developed good examples on how this could be done. And providing a better mechanism to create clarity about source and quality.

3. Integration of the format into e-knowledge reservoir. This scenario explores the integration of the common format into the EURAKNOS e-KR and is linked to session 6.

In section 5 we will look at the improvement and enhancement scenarios and will request your input for the further development of both.

7. Annex II: Consent form

Informed Consent and Information for participants

EURAKNOS e-workshop on the TN Explorers Guide
H2020 Research Project
Consent Information (provide consent on next page)

This activity is organised in the framework of the EURAKNOS research project.

The main objective of EURAKNOS is to stimulate the exchange of best practices, methodologies, and tools between the different thematic networks (linked operational groups Consent Information (provide consent on next page) and relevant linked multi-actor H2020 projects).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 817863. The data collected during the lifetime of the EURAKNOS project follow the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR).

YOUR RIGHTS AS A PARTICIPANT

Participation in this activity is voluntary, the legal basis for the processing of personal data in this interaction is 'consent'. This means that personal data, data related to your project and the results of the discussions and exercises can only be processed if you explicitly give permission for this (by signing this consent form).

You have the right to withdraw your consent at any time. However, the withdrawal of your consent shall not affect the lawfulness of processing based on your consent before its withdrawal.

At any time you have the right to:

- Ask for additional information about the processing of your data.
- Request access to the data that is stored about you.
- Request corrections if the data is incorrect or incomplete.
- Ask for information about you in a common form to be transferred to yourself or someone else.
- Ask for data to be erased or removed from you insofar as this does not threaten or threaten to seriously jeopardize the achievement and validity of the scientific research objectives.

CONFIDENTIALITY

The received data files related to your project will be hosted and stored by UGENT (Belgium) in specifically designed online shared space for EURAKNOS, protected with a password, accessible only to the EURAKNOS project partners. No sensitive personal data is or will be collected in the context of this interview.

We would like to inform you that Gent University is the joint controller of your personal data processed in the context of this research. This means that the researchers at Gent University decide on the how and why of the processing in the context of the research. Of course, they are bound by the information in this consent form.

Your personal data may possibly be consulted by some of the people working on the EURAKNOS project.

Your personal data as a research participant, will be protected and all data will be handled confidentially. Within Gent University, all staff members are bound by the 'Generic Code of Conduct

for the processing of personal data and personal information.’ In the publication(s) of the project you may be quoted. Even though your name will not be used, the quote itself might state your position as a multi-actor (e.g. farmer, advisor, policy maker, or researcher).

Consent Form

Please take the time you need to read all the info until the end and answer the survey.

1. What is your name?

2. What is your e-mail address?

3. Do you acknowledge that you understand all the info in this consent form and that you provide us with your full consent to collect and use your data in the EURAKNOS research project as described?

Yes / No

Additional Info (PRESS SUBMIT AT THE END)

These EURAKNOS activities will at times be audio/video recorded for transcription, audio recorded for publication and photographed. The records will be used for transcription and analysis.

Pictures and videos taken during the activities can be used for social media and project publication without additional consent.

The obtained data will be used to conduct further research and analyses on demonstration activities of Multi-actor projects across Europe. The data obtained will serve as a basis to draft reports to the European Commission, Directorate General for Research and Innovation, and scientific publications. Relevant general outcomes may also be used to promote use to help running and future projects in performing better. After the end of the project, UGENT will continue to store the data for five more years.

After the end of the project other researchers may have access to this data. This access will only be allowed if they agree to preserve the confidentiality of the information as requested in this form. Any personal information that could reasonably identify you will be removed or changed before files are shared with other researchers.

CONTACTS FOR QUESTIONS OR PROBLEMS

Contact Lies Harinck at lies.harinck@ugent.be (+3292646010) if you have any questions about the research or concerns about your rights as a research participant.

You also have the right to submit a complaint about how your personal data is handled, with the Belgian supervisory authority responsible for enforcing data protection legislation:

Gegevensbeschermingsautoriteit (GBA)

Drukpersstraat 35,

1000 Brussel

Tel. +32 2 274 48 00

e-mail: contact@apd-gba.be

Website: www.gegevensbeschermingsautoriteit.be

THANK YOU,

The EURAKNOS team

8. Annex III: Presentations

8.1. Webinar 1: Introduction to the "EURAKNOS Explorers' Guide

8.1.1. Presentation webinar 1

EURAKNOS

Thematic Network Explorer's guide validation e-workshop

Work Package 3 11th May 2020

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817861.

Workshop objectives

Thematic Network Explorer's guide validation workshop

What is the overall objective of the workshop (all sessions)?

- To present and discuss EURAKNOS' best experiences from finalised and ongoing Thematic Networks in terms of:
 - data collected
 - how to store data and design a platform
 - how to communicate and disseminate
 - how to manage the multi-actor approach.

What do we want from the participants?

To understand, interpret and discuss the conclusions of the EURAKNOS work and through the workshop sessions influence the output of EURAKNOS for the use of other upcoming Thematic Networks.

Workshop methodology

- Introduction webinar - 11th of May
- Reading of Thematic Network explorer's guide - 11th to 18th May
- Content discussion webinars - 18th to 20th May

Introduction Webinar - Today's agenda :

- Who is here?
- Introduction to the EURAKNOS project
- The EURAKNOS Thematic Network Explorer's Guide
- E-workshop programme 18th – 20th May
- How to select and connect
- Homework & contact for support
- Q&A

Who is here?

Got to [www.Menti.com](https://www.menti.com) and use the code:
62 18 81

1. Provide your name and say hello in your own language
2. Describe yourself in three words (in English)
3. How do you feel about today's workshop?

What is a Thematic Network?

EURAKNOS: project introduction

THE THEMATIC NETWORK EXPLORER'S GUIDE

How to design and implement Thematic Networks to maximise end-user engagement and impact

EURAKNOS

The TN explorer's guide

Purpose:

- No simple blue print solutions
- Support framework to think through and reflect on the most important elements of the process to make a TN most effective and increase impact
- A structure to support decisions making in TN specific context, capacity and timeline

Audience:

- Practitioners who are managing a TN (or MA project), starting or planning to write a TN proposal
- Potentially EU Project Officer or evaluating TN or MA projects

How to use this guide

- A roadmap to support the TN design and implementation
- Or dip into specific topics and get inspiration

The TN explorer's guide framework

Content of the TN explorer's guide

Section 1 Introduction to purpose and use of guide

Section 2 Looks at the Multi Actor Approach, how to build an MA consortium and strategy for maximising end-user engagement.

Section 3 Provides support on how to function effectively as an MA consortium

Section 4 Explores project implementation including

- end-user identification and needs assessment,
- harvesting of solution form science and practice,
- co-translation and dissemination and
- exploitation of the results to end-users

Section 5 Focusses on measuring impact and increasing your TN sustainability

Day	Time (CEST)	Webinar theme	Facilitators
18th May	10:00 – 11:00	Session 2: The roles of different actors in the Multi Actor Approach in Thematic Networks	Elodie / Sylvia / Laurens
	14:00 – 15:00	Session 3: Assessing end-user needs and identifying the best ways to harvest and co-generate user-friendly knowledge	Maxime / Patrick
19th May	10:00 – 11:00	Session 4: Designing your end-user engagement strategy	Lisa / Jessica
	14:00 – 15:00	Session 5: Improving the common format of practice abstract	Lisa / Jessica
20th May	10:00 – 11:30	Session 6: Design and strategy of the future database and how TNs can present themselves on the digital platform	Laurens / Davino / Hercules
	14:00 – 15:00	Session 7: Increasing impact and sustainability	Elodie / Sylvia

Homework !

What are we expecting from you?

- **Acting as a critical friend:** read through the Thematic Network explorer's guide
- Think about the reflection questions provided in the questionnaire (*before Thursday 14th May EOB*)
- **Sharing your Multi Actor journey:** reflect upon and draw out your collaboration journey working in a network and/or partnership with multiple actors
- **Providing expert advice:** input into scenarios for improving the common dissemination format 'Practice Abstracts'

You will receive very soon an explorer's pack containing:

- the Thematic Network Explorer's guide
- A questionnaire
- A poll (*to know which webinars sessions you are willing to participate*)
- Instructions to join all the webinars

Prepare yourself to take part in a set of webinars, next week

Sharing your Multi Actor journey

How to do the MA?

- How did the actors of your TN agree on how to work together?
- Did you report in a clear document the rules/norms for a good cooperation?
- What kind of difficulties did you face relating to the 'working together'?

Providing expert advise

- EIP-AGRI common format to facilitate knowledge flows on innovative to farmers, foresters, advisers.
- Short and concise practical information in so called 'practice abstracts'
- Central tool to spread knowledge generated by TN and other H2020 interactive innovation projects
- Various challenges related to Accessibility, Acceptability, Availability and Quality (3As and Q)

Discussion and design of scenarios to enhance end user uptake:

1. *Improvement of the current format.*
2. *Enhancement of the current format.*
3. *Integration of the format into e-knowledge reservoir.*

Closing remarks

Enjoy the journey and never stop exploring!

Questions & Answers

Who is here?

**Got to www.Menti.com and use the code:
62 18 81**

1. How was the meeting?
2. What was important?
3. How could we improve such a workshop?

THANK YOU FOR PARTICIPATING
WE LOOK FORWARD TO SEEING
YOU NEXT WEEK

What was important?

Expectations and explanation of the workshops	Mentimeter is top!	compact and fast
Do not lose the TNs results	See who is here from the previous in-person workshops	Using mentil
<small>Choose workshops where I can contribute the most. Preparing for the workshops helps to get the best results.</small>	Force the common language	Excellent format in digital way

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What was important?

Europe is smaller this way	understand the aims of Euraknos project	Good interactions
expectations on the workshop	we meet easier	Opportunity to keep the network although the bad social moment
Well organised	Time to talk and exchange	Brilliant facilitator Ilse

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What was important?

You did a great job preparing this!	Lunch together would be nice :)	Breakout rooms to make smaller interactive groups
Brilliant facilitator Ilse	Share the materials, during introductions. Would like to go deeper right away	Brainstorm with pinup.com or mural
<small>You could make an intro slide with basic info on the zoom chat box, checking microphone, etc. But great job!</small>	Already good! Simple format and good facilitation :)	I just miss the lunch and social stuff

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What was important?

If possible, find a way to avoid to have to switch screens	Brilliant facilitator Ilse
--	----------------------------

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8.2. Webinar 2

8.2.1. Presentation and feedback

EURAKNOS

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs Towards A European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

The EURAKNOS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817863

Welcome to EURAKNOS!

Thematic Network Explorer's guide validation e-workshop

18th May 2020

Workshop 2 objectives

Roles of the different actors in the MAA of TNs

Session 2 Today's agenda

- Who is here?
- Questions MAA (homework) → mentimeter to display answers from participants in order to improve the EURAKNOS Thematic Network Explorer's Guide
- Q&A

Post execution phase

Thematic Network project timeline

Pre-funding → Project implementation → Post-funding → Post-execution

Were you involved during the post-execution phase?

Q&A

What did you learn during this session?

Welcome to the TN's end user journey

What did you learn during this session?

- all TNs are facing similar challenge in conceptualisation, implementation, execution...
- The importance of the conceptualization stage
- Importance of starting in due time the proposal writing, 6-7 months before submission, having clear the topic to address and endusers
- Making a MA webinar is not so easy.
- A bit more time to exchange would have been welcome
- good to hear other experiences. But didn't learn much.
- Good initiative to organize this workshop on-line. Reducing time for traveling. Good to hear other experiences.
- Will take the survey to complete
- just in the middle of input: OGs link to TNs via Managing Authorities. 2) write in menti takes time

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What did you learn during this session?

- My impression is that there is a lot of collective knowledge among the participants in this meeting that can help improve the Guide. Good!
- I heard interesting things that could support the guide
- That it was too short.
- That people that were in the TN since conceptualization are lucky, but have a big responsibility! :D
- Some networks work better than others, a shared vision is important.
- take enough time to define the MAA in the conceptual phase
- Please mention the great tool with Facilitator agents that have existed in the Inno4Grass project.
- More actors need to be engaged early on
- We need to split up the conceptualisation phase and it can all go wrong from the start :-D

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8.3. Webinar 3

8.3.1. Presentation

EURAKNOS

EURAKNOS e-workshop

Session 3

18th May 2020 – 14:00 to 15:00

Maxime Marois – Patrick Sarzeaud IDELE- facilitators
 Ilse Rasmussen – Merete Studnitz ICROFS – moderators / co-facilitators

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817863.

Welcome to the webinar-session related to

Assessing end-user needs & identifying the best ways to harvest and co-generate user-friendly knowledge

How does this webinar work?

- Some rules
- Alternating short presentations + collection of your opinions as a TN expert and/or "knowledge users".
- What are we expecting from you?
 - Be participative
 - Share your experiences
 - Exchange best practices, recommendations, tips...
- How we will proceed to collect your opinions?

Guide presentation

• Context

Thematic Network project timeline

Needs assessment

- Who are the potential end-users?
- What do the end-users expect from TNs?
 - Evaluate the real needs of end-users
 - Aims: enhance their engagement
 - Build on their knowledge and practice

Knowledge management

- Definition
- Key steps of the process

Let's go for some interactive exercises

1) Feedbacks from participants on guide presentation

<https://app.mural.co/?test4516/m/test4516/1589439189571f0863b9276ab209f9e0612d47899ec75b2aae333>

2) Feedbacks from participants on needs assessment

<https://app.mural.co/?test4516/m/test4516/1589439870429/c1ad3022cdf0bc8f7bb3cc872cde641d519845cf>

3) Feedbacks from participants on knowledge management

<https://app.mural.co/?test4516/m/test4516/1589441188735/13a86313408aa310f174f43347ce20293e362fca>

Acknowledgements

What's next?

• At the end of this webinar, we remain at your disposal for the continuation and we are taking all your suggestions for improvement on the part treated together today.

- Contact for support
- Send an email to maxime.marois@idele.fr

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817863.

8.3.2. Feedback at webinar 3

Legend

Disagree

nothing to add | I share my idea

Agree

nothing to add | I share my idea

EURAKNOS

About the explorer's guide, assessment of your general level of understanding

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA	COMPREHENSION	VALIDATION	SUGGESTION
Guides format (length, balance between theoretical and practical input)			
Tailored to the target?			
General remarks on the topics covered in the various chapters			

EURAKNOS

What are the main end-users' characteristics to take into account to provide them the most relevant contents?

EXPECTATIONS	COMPREHENSION	VALIDATION	SUGGESTION
<p>FARMER / FORESTER:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - up to date and tailor-made, - adapted to their context and specific expectations - understandable and 'ready for use' - solutions approved - easily accessible and findable, - available in several languages (not only in English) <p>ADVISER:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - meet the farmers' knowledge needs, - share information, - facilitate connections among actors, - promote learning and dissemination - provide specific, local solutions <p>TEACHER:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - up-to-date knowledge - learn and train the facilitation skills 			

EURAKNOS

The knowledge management: the key steps of the process

STEPS OF THE PROCESS	COMPREHENSION	VALIDATION	SUGGESTION
<p>Collect</p> <p>an inventory of the existing situation is made, a bibliographical review is carried out, which consists of collecting relevant publications</p>			
<p>Co-create</p> <p>gather people to elaborate common and usable knowledge in a MA process</p> <p>Popularize the information to make it accessible and understandable and in order to disseminate the most appropriate content to farmers and foresters.</p>			
<p>Translate</p> <p>put into the right language to transfer knowledge to the end users in the objective to get it adopted</p> <p>Choice of type of dissemination forms: digital format (videos, fact sheets, podcasts...), paper to paper</p>			

8.4. Webinar 4
8.4.1. Presentation

EURAKNOS

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs Towards A European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

The EURAKNOS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817863

EURAKNOS welcomes you to Session 4:

Designing your end-user engagement strategy

TN Explorer's guide validation workshop

10-11.00 19th May 2020

Thank you for joining us!

Jessica

Lisa

Today your facilitators are

Workshop objectives

Gather your feedback

Gather your best practices

Validate with your experiences

Have fun explore and play in Mural!

Pathway 1	Pathway 2	Pathway 3
Generator	Multiplier	Dispenser
Harvesting, co-translation & and co-creation of knowledge by end-user part of and/or directly engaged with thematic network.	Upscaling of knowledge by network members to end-users beyond ones involved in thematic network e.g. not directly engaged (peer to peer)	Out-scaling of knowledge to end-users beyond the network through multimedia and other methods.
Example: Operational Groups, Innovation networks, Farm Walks	Example: on-farm demonstrations, field visits	Example: You Tube video, professional magazines

Level of intimacy →

Does the knowledge pathways framework help you to think, reflect, and identify the most effective strategies for your thematic networks?

Mentimeter

1 No

15 To some degree

7 Yes

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Please explain in which way(s) this framework helps this process? You can submit more than one idea!

shows standard approach

Different ways to think about farmer actions.

gives the main ideas and topics to tackle

Positive: each pathway represents different target groups

It shows the relationship between actors and how to communicate, disseminate and thereby increasing exploitation

to make difference into multiplier and dispenser

How to start this process? Tangible points to implement it. Be more concrete.

phasing in the project, clear target per phase

Clear definition and requirements for "ready for practice" high TRIL product technology requirement as minimum input to the TN

Mentimeter

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Please explain in which way(s) this framework helps this process? You can submit more than one idea!

Allows for a structured approach

The specific examples are helpful, e.g. "on-farm demos"

It shows the power of networks for knowledge transfer

I would prefer the terminology to be aligned with EU speak (exploitation etc). Also I think there are different "products" that can reach the end user, such as on-farm trials, farm events, but also teaching and also for example seeds.

Clear in defining the pathways to follow. Only, a major attention should be probably done to the definition of the TNEM: a step before the generator pathway

Suggests a route to add value to maximising dissemination, moving from single interactions to influencers

Helps to organize the structure at the beginning

Splits the process by managing outcomes, giving examples

basis for WP design and execution

Mentimeter

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Please explain in which way(s) this framework helps this process? You can submit more than one idea!

it could be difference not only with end-users but too in different partners responsibility

As a checklist of different ways to disseminate knowledge: use as many as possible to reach more end-users

The difference between field visits and farm walks is not clear. What about livestock and arable examples?

I agree with the idea: "Basis for WP design and execution"

Gives a good basis for defining dissemination strategy as it gives a good structure of targets

Doesn't really precise roles between stakeholders

the process is NOT linear, make it circular/interactive

Framework is impeded a little by commission rules and inflexibility i.e. if you didn't mention it in the bid, the commission won't fund it.

too generic, the process of co-creation is more complex. Examples should be provided

Mentimeter

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Please explain in which way(s) this framework helps this process? You can submit more than one idea!

too generic, the process of co-creation is more complex. Example should be provided

It's just a framework: you need offer to precise, for your project/IT which actions you will do or you have to do and so for different partners

What if there is no operational group and only a few thematic network in my country? How to collect, generate knowledge?

Interaction should be defined along with communication, dissemination and exploitation

The Hennovation example is quite vague, and doesn't say HOW these helpful aspects were achieved

Mentimeter

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Please explain in which way(s) this framework does not help this process? You can submit more than one idea!

As said before does not link to EU terminology, which I found confusing

"Level of intimacy": arrow doesn't add value + in fact, seems like opposite direction (decreasing intimacy)

the process is not linear, show it interactive/circular

Too simplistic

Distinction between Multiplier and Dispenser not clear enough (especially in the text)

Some terminology not clear, such as "end-users beyond the end-users directly involved in the thematic network"

The 3 pathways seems a linear process, stress also the circular interactivity

too generic, the process of co-creation is more complex. Example should be provided

Examples / tools mentioned might apply to several pathways

Mentimeter

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Please explain in which way(s) this framework does not help this process? You can submit more than one idea!

Gives more details how to implement each pathway.

Doesn't really precise roles between stakeholders

Too simplistic concept for knowledge transfer

What is the level of "intimacy"?

Like the egg idea, intimacy needed to get a result?

the way to interact with OGs should be presented

There often is a need for farmers to adopt new practices to their farms. There is a danger that path 2 and 3 fall back on "technology transfer" thinking.

Venn diagram? To show overlapping areas with circular arrows to show movement

look at [https://linkconsult.nl/files/Modelien%202024a_\(Engels%202024\)_Triangle%20of%20Co-creation_14d199_description_Triangle_of_Co-Creation.pdf](https://linkconsult.nl/files/Modelien%202024a_(Engels%202024)_Triangle%20of%20Co-creation_14d199_description_Triangle_of_Co-Creation.pdf)

Mentimeter

19

Please explain in which way(s) this framework helps this process? You can submit more than one idea!

shows standard approach

Different ways to think about farmer actions.

gives the main ideas and topics to tackle

Positive: each pathway represents different target groups

It shows the relationship between actors and how to communicate, disseminate and thereby increasing exploitation

to make difference into multiplier and dispenser

How to start this process? Tangible points to implement it. Be more concrete.

phasing in the project, clear target per phase

Clear definition and requirements for "ready for practice high TR, product technology requirement as minimum input to the TN"

Mentimeter

32

Please explain in which way(s) this framework helps this process? You can submit more than one idea!

Allows for a structured approach

The specific examples are helpful, e.g. "on-farm demos"

It shows the power of networks for knowledge transfer

I would prefer the terminology to be aligned with EU speak (exploitation etc). Also I think there are different "products" that can reach the end user, such as on-farm trials, farm events, but also teaching and also for example seeds.

Clear in defining the pathways to follow. Only, a major attention should be probably done to the definition of the THEM: a step before the generator pathway

Suggests a route to add value to maximising dissemination, moving from single interactions to influencers

Helps to organize the structure at the beginning

Splits the process by managing outcomes, giving examples

basis for WP design and execution

Mentimeter

32

In the Dissemination section of the Explorers Guide the statement is made that it is important to ensure best fit before best practice.

To what extent do you agree or disagree with this statement?

Strongly disagree

Strongly agree

3.7

Mentimeter

19

Please explain why you agree or disagree with this statement?

Best practice stays good example

Sometimes best fit isn't quite good enough and we have a duty to inspire using best practice to challenge people to progress.

all practice have to be adapted to the context, there is no universal practices

Best fit survives

Agree: Best practice does not imply that such a practice is suitable to all actors in all circumstances.

Farmers have to be allowed to make the final decision what fits for their situation. We have to give them the information they need to do so

It's the setting that dictates what is "best"

best practices can fit to stakeholders depending of their situation. So it's always easier to disseminate good practices. Stakeholders decide if that fit to their situation.

farmers usually are interested in only such innovations which already fully proven demonstrated under operation environment and have clear economics

Mentimeter

22

Please explain in which way(s) this framework does not help this process? You can submit more than one idea!

As said before does not link to EU terminology, which I found confusing

"Level of intimacy": arrow doesn't add value + in fact, seems like opposite direction (decreasing intimacy)

the process is not linear, show it interactive/circular

Too simplistic

The 3 pathways seems a linear process, stress also the circular interactivity

Distinction between Multiplier and Dispenser not clear enough (especially in the text)

Some terminology not clear, such as "end-users beyond the end-users directly involved in the thematic network"

Examples / tools mentioned might apply to several pathways

too generic, the process of co-creation is more complex. Example should be provided

Mentimeter

19

Please explain in which way(s) this framework does not help this process? You can submit more than one idea!

Gives more details how to implement each pathway.

Doesn't really precise roles between stakeholders

Too simplistic concept for knowledge transfer

What is the level of "intimacy"?

Like the egg idea, intimacy needed to get a result?

the way to interact with OGs should be presented

There often is a need for farmers to adopt new practices to their farms. There is a danger that path 2 and 3 fall back on "technology transfer" thinking.

Venn diagram? To show overlapping areas with circular arrows to show movement

look at [https://linkconsult.nl/files/Modelien%202014_\(Engels%202014\)_Triangle%20of%20Co-creation_141019_description_Triangle_of_Co-Creation.pdf](https://linkconsult.nl/files/Modelien%202014_(Engels%202014)_Triangle%20of%20Co-creation_141019_description_Triangle_of_Co-Creation.pdf)

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Suggests a route to add value to maximising dissemination, moving from single interactions to influencers

Helps to organize the structure at the beginning

Splits the process by managing outcomes, giving examples

basis for WP design and execution

Mentimeter

32

YOU HAVE UNTIL 5PM TODAY

What is missing from sections 2.2, 4.4 and 4.5? Please add your best practice examples!

LETS GET MURALING!

Please follow the link in the chat to Mural

EURAKNOS

Do you have any questions for us?

Please unmute your microphone if you would like to speak

EURAKNOS

Please explain in which way(s) this framework does not help this process? You can submit more than one idea!

As said before does not link to EU terminology, which I found confusing

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Mentimeter

19

In what ways (if any) has this session helped?

- Better understand the explorers guide
- highlighted different aspects
- Too see how you have used the different tools.
- Repetition of known things
- Good thing of this (and other) session(s) is that you focus on one area of the guide
- It's difficult to think, write and register what the other participants say, in particular when the session is not in your usual language
- Maybe to improve the guide
- Will help to improve the guide. Hear what others are thinking.
- inspiration by others, helps to rethink the tn i am involved, liked the mural

Mentimeter

12

In what ways (if any) has this session helped?

- Would have helped more with verbal discussion with participants.
- Interaction has helped co produce a useful guide, openness of presenters is refreshing
- provide feedbacks and insights on improving the guidelines sharing views

Mentimeter

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8.5. Webinar 5
8.5.1. Presentation

EURAKNOS

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs Towards A European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

The EURAKNOS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817863

Welcome to EURAKNOS workshop session 5

Improving the common format of practice abstract

19th May 2020 14:00 – 15:00

Thank you!

Who is here?

Why are you interested in this session about practice abstracts?

- I have to write them and hate it
- To see how we can present them on the platform
- we also have adjusted the PA format (Newbie)
- Interested in all pieces of the project, and this seems an important one
- I would like to find out how we can make them being used
- Eip agri PAs are so boring
- The format could be improved
- They aren't detailed enough to deliver value to the end user
- I'd prefer them to be more dynamic and attractive

23

Why are you interested in this session about practice abstracts?

- I wrote several and the format need to be improved
- PA's are such an integrate part of Thematic Networks but they could be improved to be more useful to end users.
- Smash the current format of PA!
- To improve ours
- Visibility of PA should be improved
- want to learn how to communicate the info, how to get to the right audience
- Farmers have mentioned that they could be useful
- I don't think that the Practice Abstract common format is a sufficient tool. How much is it used?...
- Need to make them more useful

23

Why are you interested in this session about practice abstracts?

- Make PA more searchable!
- Find out how the concept could be improved
- If they are only the EIP knowledge hub, who will find them?
- Because they are not useful, as they are they are boring and are not used
- Rip agri is not user friendly

23

AGENDA

- Introduction
- Scenario 1 Improved
- Scenario 2 Enhanced
- What's next?
- Questions

What is the purpose of this session?

To provide recommendations and propose a new EIP-AGRI set of common formats for Practice Abstracts

Remember to unmute your microphone if you want to speak & you can also add questions and comments in the Zoom chat box.

EURAKNOS

EIP-AGRI common format

Essential elements:

- ACCESSIBILITY:** Objective of the project address that are 600 characters, word count.
- ACCEPTABILITY:** Short summary for practitioners to follow language and English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count). Should at least contain the main results/outcomes of the project and the main practical recommendation(s): what would be the main advice implemented? How can this summary should be as simple and direct as possible, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out any related to cost, productivity etc. Research related aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.
- AVAILABILITY:** Description of project as no spaces; short summary (max 600 characters, word count - no spaces); short summary (1000-1500 characters, word count - no spaces).
- QUALITY:** Short summary for practitioners to follow language and English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count - no spaces). Links to other websites/websites of the project if results that are available after the project has ended, by practical communication channels that practitioners most often use.

"to facilitate knowledge flows on innovative and practice-oriented projects from the start until the end of the project"

"to provide farmers, foresters, advisers or whoever is interested with short and concise practical information in so called practice abstracts"

EURAKNOS

EURAKNOS

SCENARIO DEVELOPMENT

Really... that sound complicated?

1. Improvement of the current format.
2. Enhancement of the current format.
3. Integration of the current format

EURAKNOS

Scenario 1 Improvement of the current format.

Question?

Please go to Mural

- Better search function
- Mandatory links to information in different formats
- Clear link to source of information

EURAKNOS

AGENDA

- Introduction
- Scenario 1 Improved
- Scenario 2 Enhanced
- What's next?
- Questions

What is the purpose of this session?

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Remember to unmute your microphone if you want to speak & you can also add questions and comments in the Zoom chat box.

EURAKNOS

QUESTIONS?

Do you have any questions for us?

Please do not hesitate to provide further comments and feedback by email.

EURAKNOS

SCENARIO DEVELOPMENT

Really... that sound complicated?

1. Improvement of the current format.
2. Enhancement of the current format.
3. Integration of the current format

EURAKNOS

Scenario 1 Improvement of the current format.

Question?

Please go to Mural

- Better search function
- Mandatory links to information in different formats
- Clear link to source of information

EURAKNOS

In what ways (if any) has this session helped?

Mentimeter

- reliving accumulated tension and frustration
- Confirmation of our experiences
- Got some inspiration for representing them on the farmbook
- It was interesting, thank you.
- If the eip-agri PA format is improved, it will be as great help!
- Thinking about the PA now, and not when we're in a rush to write 150 in the next 2 weeks
- Good to know that PA format will be developed
- Knowing that everybody struggles with the same issues
- giving his opinion on PA, participate in the creation of the future PA hoping this one will be useful and used by farmers

13

In what ways (if any) has this session helped?

Mentimeter

- it definitely showed the need to improve the PA
- It stresses the need for a common platform which is easily accessible for farmers
- A chance to realise there is a common problem, frustrating to know it has not been addressed
- Seeing that we are all in the same boat and we're all thinking along the same ideas for improvement

13

8.5.2. Feedback at webinar 5

Scenario 1 Improvement of the current format.

Feedback notes:

- Too much project specific information
- Need catchy headlines
- Summary is too short
- Have the project have an editorial board with end-users
- add real titles instead of just PA1, PA2, etc.
- Better search function
- Allow links to other materials which provide more feedback on the topic
- Allow pictures and allow more links to websites
- Less wording, more schematic
- pictures/illustrations?
- Mandatory links to information in different formats
- Clear link to source of information
- including pics, video's
- more visibility on search engines
- This is a time to have no need to have more flexibility
- Would be wonderful if there is no need to have more formats side by side, so lets give more flexibility
- Looks like there is an option to add a link to the article
- It doesn't seem like it's a practical information which is feasible
- Ability to add images and links would be good
- One project was involved with us but we limited paper reviews, although some containing produced more user friendly outputs
- a change in the abstract. They are approached as a necessary need to be included if the abstract was different the content might improve
- Make them all appear under the same title as one PA but not a sub-section
- Practice abstract 1
- Practice abstract 2
- Comment section should be available to have opportunity to give feedback
- Direct access and (full text/ metadata) search function for all PAs
- Search by the title. This needs to be bigger and the first thing to read
- Short summary for practitioners in English
- Lighting in layer hen houses influences egg production and plays a role in the prevention of various feather pecking. With the phasing out of incandescent lights, farmers are looking for alternative light sources that are efficient and suitable to install in various housing systems. LED lights are durable, shockproof and low in energy use. Although they have a flat size current which doesn't flicker, the electronic dimming may produce flickering. This can cause stress to the hen, which can lead to feather pecking. Dimming should therefore be done without flickering or with very high flicker frequency. Small size LEDs can fit easily into rotary or rotary systems. By combining various types of LED or putting a coating on many colours of light can be produced and even the UV spectrum. It could prevent LED lights produce visible light, but a narrow light spectrum advised for egg producing animals, and for rearing pullets a cooler 8000K. When buying LED you attention to:
 - The position for LED is essential to high-pressure water cleaning and concentrations of ammonia
 - Main aim the dimming spectrum of your LED light is other for use versus or very high in flicker frequency
 - Check a wide and narrow beam type of LED with variable electronics
- Search by the title. This needs to be bigger and the first thing to read
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 - The position for LED is essential to high-pressure water cleaning and concentrations of ammonia
 - Main aim the dimming spectrum of your LED light is other for use versus or very high in flicker frequency
 - Check a wide and narrow beam type of LED with variable electronics

You can add sticky notes by using your right mouse button. And you can enlarge your screen by using your scroll wheel on your mouse.

Scenario 2 Enhancement of the current

I like the idea of a free for all when it comes to factsheets, but there does need to be some minimum content otherwise its just a lot of pretty pages

If more extensive change could be made, how would a PA look like?

Result of a survey on the most used digital tools by farmers: the videos are the most used. To reach farmer need to have a video (could be coupled with fact sheet or toolbox)

Sharing or rating function

Sharing +1

Ideas and Animations?

videos, links to our YouTube channel would be good - more farmer friendly

Lots of links to maximise additional resources

PA could be a newsletter send by EIP Agri

Videos are great! These are proof that really works. But short descriptions are also needed.

We had a rating option but readers did not use this one.

A common format has advantages so search functions can be build around it.

Only if you have uses of the search function

Toolboxes

A nice and well prepared diagram does not replace a descriptive text

Toolboxes are really practical and useful what farmers need. Process descriptions are very important.

What is a toolbox? So many out there

See an example I like: <https://repository.incredibleforest.net>

www.encyclopediapratisensis.eu is an e-knowledge reservoir about grassland with both fact sheets, more deep case studies, technical leaflets, links to our YouTube videos, award winners and a syllabus on grassland made in our project Inno4Grass

Minimum single page of A4 and contains a short protocol context and cost benefit analysis

Should be designed to change behaviour not just inform on a task

the search function could link to all the relevant format - eg you search sheep milking and you get a link to a factsheet, and video for this instance

Consider the output format

I like this format, contains some structure of fact sheet a very good

This looks very interesting and attractive.

Change the format to pictures, video and charts

and pictograms

WEAKNESSES

INTERNATIONAL STUDIES

Too short for PA, would need more info

Infographics are good for the general public, farmers like fact sheets, policy makers prefer information briefs

Fact Sheets?

Fact sheets should contain some sections (practical use - economics - legal framework ...) these should answer the farmers questions

Fact sheets are useful

I don't think we should have a standard format for factsheet - just a page limit. Again, trying to use existing resources from the project, not adding another layer of repeating the information

Fact sheets are used by farmers. To be effective need to be a short fact sheet (2p max) with videos, pictures and schemes

link to factsheets would be great. Especially since we develop them already in some projects. So, no repetition/duplicate of work

Fact sheet should contain links with more info e.g: videos, websites, KR...

Use a common title to engage an open content like 'The Body' where content changes (videos, etc)

Have a section of 'Further information' with links

All the Practice Abstracts prepared by the AgriLink project in the EIP-AGRI common format can be found here: https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/find_connect/projects/agri-link_agricultural_knowledge_linking_farmers

have some cost/benefit analysis format as well - this is what is asked in the latest TNs.

Use a format end users are familiar with already

Who should be involved in developing a PA?

We are not actually addressing the speech bubble question WHO should be involved?

Source of information should be precised

end users should be involved in developing the format and validating the content

We might have to allow the users to give feedback, it takes time

There should be a kind of quality check if we want farmers to use the PAs.

Quality control needed by EC

Farmers, advisors as practical validators and input providers.

What contextual information should be included? Country, farm type, rainfall, soils, supply chains?

there should be some information about under which conditions the info will work

8.6. Webinar 6

8.6.1. Presentation

EURAKNOS

Designing the EURAKNOS High Impact Knowledge Reservoir

Session #6
Design and strategy of the future database and how TNs can present themselves on the digital platform

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817863.

SETUP & CONCLUSIONS

SETUP (1/3)

2 Sections

- Section 1: Feedback on the EURAKNOS database model
Goal: communicate in a clear way the EURAKNOS database model & how Thematic Networks can make use of the model to integrate data in a central database.
Outcome: positive feedback from participants on the data base model
- Section 2: How to present TN output on the EURAKNOS platform
Goal: validate learnings & assumptions on (a) added value of EURAKNOS platform, (b) how to present a TN on the platform, (c) how to present a TN's output on the platform
Outcome: clear validation on EURAKNOS assumptions, positive interacton & feedback

SETUP (2/3)

Format & Tools

- Format:
 - Presentation of learnings & assumptions
 - Interactive session to gather feedback
- Tools:
 - Webinar via Zoom
 - Feedback via PollEverywhere

SETUP (3/3)

Methodology Poll Everywhere results

- All results are clustered in categories
- The number indicates how many times this answer was given
- The results are ranked by votes they got during the poll
- In this [document](#), you can find all the raw data of the poll

PRESENTATION USED DURING WORKSHOP

Let's try out 'Poll Everywhere'

1. Go to www.pollev.com/eureka426
2. Enter your name
3. You're ready to answer the questions

SECTION 1 Feedback on the EURAKNOS database model

Presentation outline

- Introduction
- What lies beneath...
- The four pillars of the EURAKNOS HIKR design
- What is a data model and why do we need it?
- The methodology behind our model
- Defining the concept of Thematic Networks
- Identifying entities, entity attributes, and relations
- Classes of the EURAKNOS data model
- Relations of the EURAKNOS data model
- Class properties of the classes "Output", "Creator", and "Thematic Network"
- The EURAKNOS data model
- Next steps
- How can TNs utilise the EURAKNOS data model?

Introduction

- The **aim** of this presentation is to make known the **conceptual design** that has taken place in the context of EURAKNOS, which has led to the creation of the **EURAKNOS data model**.
- The **objectives** of the presentation are to:
 - outline the **basic pillars** of the EURAKNOS HIKR design;
 - highlight the **importance** of the **conceptual design process** and its **output** (i.e. the data model);
 - briefly outline the **data model development process**;
 - describe the **building blocks** of the EURAKNOS data model;
 - present the **EURAKNOS data model** in its entirety;
 - show what **steps** are thought to be taken next;
 - stimulate a discussion on how TNs can benefit from the HIKR design.

What lies beneath...

The TN KRs landscape

- A **number of metaphors** have been employed by the existing TNs to make agriculture-related content and information available:
 - KR as a **catalogue** with an emphasis on the provision of functionalities for assisting and supporting the user in the search and retrieval of digital content.
 - KR as a **library** with an emphasis on the classification of digital content with regard to the types of data objects available and the topics addressed.
 - KR as a **practical, digital guidebook** with an emphasis on the provision of ready-to-use and easy-to-apply solutions tailored to the needs of the end users targeted.
 - KR as a **marketplace (for the exchange of good practices)** with an emphasis on redirecting the user to web-based information environments of interest.
- Various metaphors adopted → a range of information architectures → various designs → **heterogeneity** in data structures.

The four pillars of the EURAKNOS HIKR design

What is a data model and why do we need it?

The methodology behind our model

Defining the concept of Thematic Networks

Thematic networks are multi-actor projects that focus on a **theme**. The theme of a Thematic Network relates to a **domain**. Thematic Networks aim to disseminate easy to understand and apply information in the form of useful, practical **outputs** (practice abstracts, manuals, reports, infographics, videos, etc.). Outputs available by a Thematic Network can be distinguished into documents, software applications, presentations, images, audio and video objects, and datasets. Outputs are made available to end users (e.g. farmers, foresters, advisors) and have specific **types** and **formats**. Each output has a **purpose** (i.e. a reason for which it has been created), a **topic** (relevant to the Thematic Network's domain) and has been created by a **creator**. Creators can be distinguished into **organisations** and **individuals** (who are affiliated with organisations). Organisations are involved in Thematic Networks either as **leading** or **participating** partners

Identifying entities, entity attributes, and relations

- A number of statements, helping to identify **entities**, **entity attributes** and **relations between entities**, can be derived from the definition:
 - A **Thematic Network is about a theme**, and the **theme relates to a domain**. Thus, a Thematic Network **relates to a domain**.
 - An **output is intended to be used by (specific types of) end users**.
 - There are **different kinds of outputs**: documents, software applications, presentations, audio and video objects, images, and datasets.
 - An output has a (topic, purpose, type, format).
 - An output is **created by a creator**. A creator is an individual or organisation.
 - An individual is **affiliated with an organisation**.
 - An organisation has a specific type of involvement in the Thematic Network (participating/leading partner).

Classes of the EURAKNOS data model

Relations between classes

Class properties: the "Output" class

- title** = the title of an output of a TN
- titleLanguage** = the language(s) in which the title of an output is made available
- description** = textual description of what an output is about
- descriptionLanguage** = the language(s) in which the textual description of an output is available
- contentLanguage** = the language(s) in which the content of an output is available
- keywords** = a list of keywords that are associated with an output of the Thematic Network
- keywordLanguage** = the language(s) in which an output-related keywords are made available
- url** = URL to the "source" of the output (where applicable)
- comment** = comment(s) from users of the output that may be probably available
- aggregrating** = the overall rating that has been made to an output of a Thematic Network
- dateCreated** = the date on which an output was created
- accessibleForFree** = a flag to signal whether an output is accessible for free or not
- license** = a description of specific licensing terms (e.g. a Creative Commons license) that describe how an output may be further exploited
- geographLocation** = the geographic location (country/ies) to which the content of an output (for instance, solution to a problem or innovative practice) relates
- version** = the version of a Thematic network's output that is available
- purpose** = The reason/purpose for which an output has been produced (e.g. access to data, communication, dissemination, education/training)
- fileSize** = The size of the file (in KB/MB) through which an output of a TN is available

Class properties: the "Creator" class

- name** = the name of an output creator
- description** = a short textual description of the output creator
- country** = the country of origin of an output creator

Class properties: the "Thematic Network" class

- acronym** = the acronym of the TN (e.g. EURAKNOS)
- fullName** = the full name of the Thematic Network (e.g. Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs: towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System)
- url** = URL of the Thematic Network's website
- description** = textual description of what the Thematic Network is about
- relatesTo** = relationship between the "Thematic Network" class and the "Domain" class; i.e. a Thematic Network relates to one or more Domains
- coordinatedBy** = relationship between the "Thematic Network" class and the "Organisation" class; i.e. One or zero Thematic Networks are coordinated by an Organisation

The EURAKNOS data model

Poll Everywhere

1. Go to www.polleverywhere.com/eureka426
2. Enter your name
3. You're ready to answer the questions

Do you believe that the technical design we've presented today already captures the core features of the output of your TN?

Next steps

What pieces of information (i.e. metadata) would you like to be provided with when a digital output of a TN is being delivered to you?

Top

Start the presentation to see live content. For screen share software, share the entire screen. Get help at pollev.com/app

Results

Key info about metadata	
Title	
Author(s)/creator/organisation/source (and its contact information)	
Summary/abstract	
Language(s)	
Subject	
Links for further information	
Keywords (e.g. antimicrobials, performance, yield, cost of production)	
Type of output - file type or format (video, document, etc.)	
Date of data creation	
Country of origin	
Domain	
Anything that's boosts SEO	
Review	
Maturity of the best practice	
Uptake or popularity of the practice	
Number of visitors, downloads, views, etc.	
Efficiency	

Results (2/2)

Other	Dis/Cite Standard
	Dis/Cite Standard
	Open access
	I suggest you present a short selection of metadata as default (URL, creator, ...) but it should be possible to see all if the user wishes to
	training material level
	Costs

How can TNs utilise the EURAKNOS HIKR?

Conclusions on section 1

- Section 1 focused on the presentation of the EURAKNOS data model.
- The aim of the presentation that has been delivered by the AUA team was to provide the rationale behind this endeavor, as well as present the methodology employed and its steps together with its end result (i.e. the data model).
- The workshop session was attended by approximately 30 participants. It can be said that there was an interest in the work presented.
- In order to facilitate the understanding of the data model a presentation of its concrete building block took place (together with the explanations necessary), prior to showing the data model in its entirety.
- Issues that have been also highlighted related to: (i) a number of scenarios identified with regard to the way(s) in which Thematic Networks could take advantage of the EURAKNOS data model; (ii) the steps to be taken next.

Conclusions on section 1

- The interest of the audience can be manifested by the comments/queries posted in the chat box during the presentation. These posts related mostly to comments, additional remarks or requests for clarifications. In some cases, the session participants attempted to draw links to their own TN's particularities and characteristics and find out how the EURAKNOS model could fit.
- The presentation included two questions aimed to be responded by the participants. The first questions intended to elicit the responses of the audience with regard to whether the EURAKNOS model can successfully capture TN-related data object details. The second question (an open one), was used with the aim to prompt the participants provide their insights with regard to what metadata should be made available for a TN data object (as information that a user can have access to when retrieving the data object from the EURAKNOS platform).
- A first conclusion that can be made with regard to the question responses received is that the EURAKNOS data model has captured almost all the details that the participants consider as important when it comes to TN-related data objects. A more thorough review of these responses will help determine whether any minor adaptations will have to be considered.

SECTION 2 HOW TO PRESENT TN OUTPUT ON THE EURAKNOS PLATFORM

What will Farmbook look like?

At this moment, we are designing high level wireframes to communicate about the overall structure of farmbook. Wireframes describe how the content of the website should look like, they are no visual representation of the website.

What will Farmbook look like for you?

With this participatory workshop we want to get some insights on the position of the Thematic Networks in the platform and what Farmbook could mean for your organisation.

We will guide you through some questions and options and would like to get some feedback from you. If you see interesting answers of other participants, don't hesitate to "like" them with our used tool.

Results

What are the benefits of adding your TN output to the EURAKNOS database?	Count
Sustainability and legacy of TN output	6
Ensure longevity beyond the project's lifetime	1
Reaching to a wide range of end users	4
One place to find information in a common open access database	7
More impact, more voices to shout about best practices	3
More visibility for the TNs	1
Similar structure across TNs building on outputs	1
Critical mindset for the output	1
Avoiding duplications (for new projects)	1

Results

What are potential blockers for you to upload your TN output to the EURAKNOS database?	Count
Time and resources - projects with budget for website, may need adaptation of future funding	4
Having data in proper format & (re-)work on the metadata of the outputs	7
Language (same information in multiple languages but no supporting SEO also in that language)	1
IPR (Intellectual property rights)	1
Too many themes make the search function too broad and flat	2
Responsibility after TN project ends	1
Bureaucracy	1
Support from EC in the long term	1
Don't see any blockers, TN are about free accessible information	1
Ease of use	1

- ## Three ways to represent your TN's output
- Your Thematic Network "tagged" as a source of the output
 - Have a list of all TNs, with a brief explanation & a link to the website of each TN.
 - Have a full page about my TN.
-

1. Your Thematic Network “tagged” as a source of the output

2. Have a list of all TNs, with a brief explanation & link to the website

3. Have a full page about my TN

In what way do you wish to represent your TN output in the EURAKNOS platform?

Results

Which features of your current TN-website are most important to you?		Count
Search	Good search function (sorted by relevance)	1
	Interactive data bases	1
Materials	Keywords specific to our sector	1
	The best practice materials including (storytelling) videos	2
	Good practices repository	1
	Information and contacts to organisation leading the Hubs	2
	Possibility to rate information	1
	End user narratives	1
	Articles and short reports	1
	Automatic output generation (in HTML and PDF) from an online database	1
Website	Visually attractive and engaging for end users	2
	Our MapViewer tool (Best practices search)	1
	Newsletter sign up	1
	Automatic output generation (in HTML and PDF) from an online database	1

Results

Which of these features would you rather 'outsoure' to the EURAKNOS platform?	Trending Score
Good practices database	3
A social media function through which stakeholders can interact online	3
Final outputs	2
The database	2
Rating function like social media	1
Mapping tool	1
The online database that creators fill in to generate the outputs	1
Outputs	0

Results

What have you learned during the session?
Nice clear presentation from Hercules
I think the TN explorer's guide has not enough information about what we have spoken in this session
interesting and very useful.
Nice example of use of interactive tools for virtual meetings
A 60 min session is too short! 90 min is fine!
How to not hide small areas behind bigger ones?
interesting to share the different projects through a platform
More projects are needed to encourage sharing and connectivity between projects
a common database could be possible. Question is the timing and the future interactions between the different networks?
A hope that a common Knowledge reservoir could be possible at EU level?
The links which could exist in the future between TN and Euraknos
EURAKNOS offers interesting features for TN, but doesn't solve the need for a permanent structure. Keep the pressure on!
I saw tendencies of interlinking of KR/TN
interesting stuff about the database "iceberg"
How much work goes into the back end to make the front end work as efficiently as possible
We need more transversal projects like this!

Next steps

Process feedback into wireframes

We will keep you up to date of the process

Thank you for
participating!

8.7. Webinar 7
8.7.1. Presentation

EURAKNOS

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs Towards A European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

The EURAKNOS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817863

Welcome to EURAKNOS!

Thematic Network Explorer's guide validation e-workshop

20th May 2020

Workshop 7 objectives

Increasing impact and sustainability

Session 2 Today's agenda

- Who is here? mentimeter
- Questions MAA (homework) → Mural/ mentimeter to display answers from participants in order to improve the EURAKNOS Thematic Network Explorer's Guide
- Q&A

Reminder Homework session 7

CHAPTER 5: MEASURING YOUR IMPACT AND TN SUSTAINABILITY
(For session 6 & 7)

General questions

1. Is there anything missing in this chapter?
2. Please provide any relevant examples for the good practices boxes

Homework MURAL

Is there anything missing in chapter 5?

Go to mural - link also in chat

[s://app.mural.co/t/glz4304/m/glz4304/1589896377867/ee81e4508e72af92029e7c684b8089fe](https://app.mural.co/t/glz4304/m/glz4304/1589896377867/ee81e4508e72af92029e7c684b8089fe)

Homework Mural

Please provide relevant concrete examples for the good practices boxes (use the same session as for the previous question)

How do you measure short-term impact of your project? Please give concrete examples if possible.

website connections	metrics on communications	Social media and website analytics
Followers on twitter and other social media	number of downloads	Direct contact with end users during the project
Attendees at events/workshops etc	Number of "knowledge items" shared, number of participants engaging (at events and on social media; uptake of practices is more difficult to measure).	number of contacts during the project

How do you measure short-term impact of your project? Please give concrete examples if possible.

Small surveys during events (face to face not written)	participants to events organised by the project (farm demonstration, conference...)	compare to KPIs, defined at start
Surveys, number of clicks, phone calls, face to face meetings	metrics on communications: tweets, website visits, number of articles published, number of stakeholders registered, number of attendees in events	ST impact should (also) be coupled to (ST) objectives you had with your project
direct feedback from people	From experience in other projects or roles, mid-term surveys and reviews can be very insightful and helpful	Feedback/surveys evaluating events/workshops etc

How do you measure short-term impact of your project? Please give concrete examples if possible.

CORE Organic network has continuous monitoring of the activities from the start until the end - special monitoring group	acceptance on scale 1-5, before and after demo	We use analytics etc but this is uptake and still not impact. We have suggested using the cost benefit analysis coupled with analytics and then uptake curve to hypothesise the impact.
I have seen collection some information also at registration to event.	Ask end users to give their impact, changes they have made, focus groups, workshops, surveys to gather data	glasses of beer during exchange
social media followers, number of participants at the events, number of downloads.	testimonials	Involvement of stakeholders in meetings

How do you measure short-term impact of your project? Please give concrete examples if possible.

No of registrations to the the TN network	Observing how end-user interact with the material.	number of letters of intent
talking with stakeholders involved in the thematic you meet if they know the project/TN	copy of other projects also using this webinar approach. (already in Enabling next week)	

Go to mural - link also in chat

s://app.mural.co/t/glz4304/m/glz4304/1589896377867/ee81e4508e72af92029e7c684b8089fe

Homework Mural

Please provide relevant concrete examples for the good practices boxes (use the same session as for the previous question)

If yes, how do you allocate budget in the project proposal for monitoring the short-term impact?

Planning aspect: it would require that the actions or initiatives whose impact you want to monitor need to be finished well before the end of the project.	in the wp where assessment is made	WP allocation for dissemination and events
User surveys, with involvement of survey experts (sampling, how to phrase questions)	time and money for speaking in conference or other events	Deliverable from impact workshop
Separate WP would be required - other than dissemination and communication or outreach	Identify a few monitoring / measurement strategies, then try to estimate the costs for each before deciding how much is needed and appropriate	don't agree on extra wp, should be linked in content

If yes, how do you allocate budget in the project proposal for monitoring the short-term impact?

If I had to allocate a budget for this, it would be to build a tool for all partners to easily collect their impacts.	Agree with dedicated WP. Serves different purpose to C&D	It is difficult for a coordinator to assess the impact since he/she already has its coordinating tasks
Digital platform to share impact from end users	Monitoring is needed to adjust the comm/diss strategy	niva has template for kpi, useful for impact
You could assign an impact supervisor who has to monitor impact throughout all the related tasks	Extend the duration of the project to do this task.	You need to develop a comprehensive framework to assess impact including economic, ecologic, ST vs LT, level of adoption by target group... Framework will also depend on your project and your TN

How do you measure short-term impact of your project? Please give concrete examples if possible.

CORE Organic network has continuous monitoring of the activities from the start until the end - special monitoring group	acceptance on scale 1-5, before and after demo	We use analytics etc but this is uptake and still not impact. We have suggested using the cost benefit analysis coupled with analytics and then uptake curve to hypothesize the impact.
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Homework Mural

Please provide relevant concrete examples for the good practices boxes (use the same session as for the previous question)

Based on your experience, which other activities might boost TNs impact and make its results more sustainable?

Invest in follow up initiatives based on the project outcomes

It's scary, but reaching out to local and regional media organizations to get increase visibility

Put "Impact" central in all activities - each activity should eventually contribute to creating impact

Demonstration events with end-users participating

Continuous dissemination of the network results

Work with EURAKNOS

International travel: hard to get people 1st time, easy next time

Full engagement of stakeholders, especially organisations and institutions

Make use of existing platforms before setting up new one.

Based on your experience, which other activities might boost TNs impact and make its results more sustainable?

Results should feed into an open source living reservoir.

Consult most relevant stakeholders continuously about which output they need and how it should be organized, presented, create ownership.

Maintaining an active social media presence

Cross visits

disseminate the results on email conferences read by many people (ex : : educational),

Europa as theme: people are really connected to something that populist politicians neglect and misuse

Involving end-users at all stages so they are engaged from the beginning and offer greater access to networks not available to academic/other institutes

Share tools Follow up projects to build on existing TNs

Link with national and regional organisations that are active in that area, bring them in as partners.

How do you measure short-term impact of your project? Please give concrete examples if possible.

CORE Organic network has continuous monitoring of the activities from the start until the end - special monitoring group

acceptance on scale 1-5, before and after demo

We use analytics etc but this is uptake and still not impact. We have suggested using the cost benefit analysis coupled with analytics and then uptake curve to hypothesise the impact.

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Ask end users to give their impact, changes they have made, focus groups, workshops, surveys to gather data

glasses of beer during exchange

social media followers, number of participants at the events, number of downloads.

testimonials

Involvement of stakeholders in meetings

How do you measure short-term impact of your project? Please give concrete examples if possible.

No of registrations to the the TN network

Observing how end-user interact with the material.

number of letters of intent

talking with stakeholders involved in the thematic you meet if they know the project/TN

copy of other projects also using this webinar approach. (already in Enabling next week)

How do you make your Thematic network sustainable after the completion of the project?

If good and useful relationships have been formed they will continue.

Convince a hosting organisation with recurrent funding to keep the TN alive

Make sure most important stakeholders are part of the project (steering group etc) make use of their websites

By creating network around the topics that have broader societal relevance

(Yes, mostly answered in previous one) The topic of this morning's session: a well-organized, searchable database and at least one permanent web page

Maintain facilitators within the consortium

The Organic Farm Knowledge hub was set up in one project that has since been used in several others. Some core partners are committed to keeping it alive.

Connecting to national rural networks and Eip agri and chambers.

4d4f used flemish sensor dbase

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How do you make your Thematic network sustainable after the completion of the project?

Develop a plan for the future AFTER the project and get people involved

For Organic PLUS, some results are placed on French database Biobase and Eu database Organic eprints

Connect to national gate keepers

National funders

National funders

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How do you make your TN outputs sustainable after the completion of the project?

That's why we have hope for EURAKNOS

Individual partners can make use of the outputs in their own workstreams

With a good dissemination plan :)

to put documents and video on database

Involving stakeholders from the start of the project

in Oppla.eu: free life-long hosting

Make outputs open access

The example of the organic farm knowledge hub is also relevant here.

the networks ARE output, a bit confusing split of network and output

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How do you make your TN outputs sustainable after the completion of the project?

can be stored in Zenodo

Allocate an organisation to take over the website to maintain website, update outputs etc

to choose to have a webpage on a existing website and not a special not sustainable TN website

Depends on type of output - in some cases it's a matter of storing, in other cases it's more about keeping momentum

please send the oppla link in the chat!!!

Being active after the project, consortium partners keep disseminating results on their own channels

Non sustainable networks is why sometimes farmer's resist engaging

This is very big-picture, but perhaps the best way is to keep the larger EURAKNOS project going! If it proves to be successful.

Open Access archives - for organic sector for instance Organic Eprints

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Thank you for your attention

If you wish to further contribute, please indicate in which way we can contact you for the TN explorers guide contribution. Feel free to indicate your ideas into Mural until the end of the week.

